

Report on Research Line 3

Leveraging Behavioural Change for Inclusive Energy Communities

Insights from ACCTING's Experimental Research

Research Cycle 2

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Please cite as: Boostani, P., Vilhelmsen, K., Pellegrini Masini, G., Quinti, G., Pugliese, F., & Cacace, M. (2025). *ACCTING Report on Research Line 3: Leveraging Behavioural Change for Inclusive Energy Communities*. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525880

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees the efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Find out more: <https://accting.eu>

Acknowledgment of funding

The ACCTING project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no. 101036504.

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Introduction and methodology

This report presents a summary of findings from ACCTING's second cycle of experimental studies, which entailed 87 quasi-experimental case studies conducted across thirteen countries between December 2023 and August 2024. Each of the eight research lines explores sustainability and behavioural change within the framework of a specific European Green Deal policy area — including climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. The Research Line 3 report focuses on what variables influence the outcome of energy community projects involving vulnerable individuals and aiming at reducing energy vulnerability, and what variables in communities influence the behaviour of individuals (at both individual and collective levels) who promote, join and participate in energy communities that reduce energy vulnerability.

All reports are available at <https://accting.eu/project-deliverables/>

1. Introduction

The aim of ACCTING is to produce knowledge and innovation from a gender+ intersectional perspective to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels and contribute towards policy development for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal (GD).

The overarching questions addressed in ACCTING's research are:

- *What factors enable or hinder individual, collective and organisational behaviours and related social practices to achieve a gender-equal and socially just environmental transition across different Green Deal policy areas?*
- *How are these factors the same/different for various (vulnerable) groups, considering also intersectional dynamics?*

In the first research cycle, each research line (RL) addressed these questions in a broad, exploratory manner. The second cycle is explanatory, allowing each of the RLs to break down these generic questions into more specific research questions adapted to the RLs' research themes and aims. A case study methodology was implemented to deepen the insights gained at the previous research stages, by especially:

- Analysing interdependencies across experimental studies between behaviours and inequality/vulnerability factors.
- Identifying and analysing strategies that seem to fit best to most of the configurations identified for enabling (1) behavioural change and (2) transformative change without reproducing gender inequalities.

The methods are chosen in line with the thematic aim, considering how what needs to be gauged can be measured (validity) so that it follows comparable methods across all experimental studies within the RL3 (reliability). In the second cycle of RL3, the following questions have been addressed:

- What variables influence the outcome of energy community projects involving vulnerable individuals and aiming at reducing energy costs?
- What variables in communities influence the behaviour of individuals who promote or join and participate in energy communities that reduce energy poverty?

1.1 Sustainability and Transformation in RL3

According to Linner and Wibeck (2019), societal transformation implies non-linear systematic changes in a society's social, financial, environmental and political aspects. The transformation toward sustainability explores how researchers and policymakers can effectively improve energy systems and energy consumption behaviour within a society to address climate change (Tvaronaciene and Slusarczyk, 2019).

According to the definition above, we concentrate on three pillars of sustainability: environmental, social and economic (Purvis et al., 2019). Environmental sustainability in RL3 includes taking sustainable actions to promote clean energy, such as optimising energy use and transitioning to renewable energy sources. As for the social aspect, our focus is on inclusivity, equality and ensuring accessible energy services for all people, especially vulnerable groups and individuals. The financial aspects of RL3 involve supporting financial inclusivity, stability and affordability.

Moreover, in RL3, transformation involves a significant shift in energy systems, societal norms, and individual and collective behaviours to adopt more environmentally sustainable and equitable community practices. Behavioural transformation refers to sustainable changes in energy consumption, such as reducing consumption, engaging in energy communities and being active in sustainable community energy projects (e.g., workshops, training sessions, discussions, meetings, etc.). This understanding of transformation places this research in the context of a broad disciplinary debate on the leading factors influencing behavioural change in relation to the energy transition (Steg et al., 2015).

1.2 Behavioural change at individual and collective levels in RL3

Behavioural change means adapting a new behaviour based on people's motivation, among other things, to change to a desired behaviour (Hagger et al., 2020). According to Hagger et al. (2020, p.17), "Behaviour change is often said to proceed in stages, from pre-contemplation through contemplation, preparation, action and maintenance."

As Pellegrini-Masini (2020) mentions, what individuals consider positive for themselves could impact the community on collective matters. Therefore, analysing behavioural change at the individual level is important. Personal factors like beliefs and routines, cultural and social context, education and knowledge about sustainable energy, as well as accessibility to energy services, all influence behavioural change at the individual level (Steg et al., 2015; Kauppi, 2015). Further, according to Kauppi (2015), behavioural change at the individual level is influenced by role models (e.g. individuals who follow sustainable practices) and those who have authority.

In research line three, individual behavioural change refers to changes towards a more sustainable lifestyle regarding energy and other pro-environmental and pro-social behaviours. Transitioning to sustainable energy means that future energy systems will increasingly rely on renewable sources (Steg et al., 2015). To achieve this transition, it is essential to understand the factors and conditions that influence individuals' willingness to adapt and change their energy consumption behaviours (Steg et al., 2015). Examples of pro-environmental behaviours include starting, organising or joining a community energy scheme, participating actively in an energy community, learning new information about sustainable practices, and implementing pro-

environmental behaviours such as energy conservation, sustainable mobility, purchasing organic foods, and more.

Examples of pro-social behaviours include participating in social activities besides the energy community's operational meetings, making new friends, and creating mutual support activities among community members, such as financial support for the weakest members and providing free services or goods for the needy.

In research line three, collective behavioural change refers to any changes in actions by the community energy projects regarding the project's design, planning and implementation and how these actions affect relevant vulnerable groups. Social norms, culture and policy changes within a community or society can influence both individual and collective behaviours. According to Marchi et al. (2023), following pro-environmental behaviour and participating in the energy transition rely on people's awareness and willingness to change.

As earlier defined, collective behaviours in energy communities can shape the frequency and scope of sustainable actions, as well as influence pro-social behaviours. Community energy projects encourage behavioural change by offering incentives and support to help members stay committed to shared goals (Chabay, 2020, p. 153).

The intertwined nature of individual and collective behaviours is particularly evident in the social research area focusing on energy communities where the actions of individuals contribute both to sustainable energy generation, conservation and consumption, but at the same time, they are part of a collective action to improve the community's sustainability (Heiskanen et al., 2010; Pellegrini-Masini, 2020).

1.3 Research design

1.3.1. Criteria for selection of cases

Since September 2023, the ACCTING partners involved in RL3 have engaged with case studies across Norway, Italy, Denmark and Austria. Initially, cases were screened and researched via desk research through the web, later, they were contacted via e-mail to introduce the ACCTING project and the second research cycle. Subsequently, we organised online meetings and calls with project leaders and potential contacts to vet the cases for inclusion in our study.

Three main criteria for inclusion were outlined based on the Plan - ~~Obj~~ (see Appendix A) as follows:

- Vulnerability profile

The case had to involve individuals deemed vulnerable following the classification earlier employed in the ACCTING project (see D2.1). In RL3, we considered relevant vulnerabilities economic disadvantage, foreign ethnic background, old or young age, living in a rural or remote location (islands), and gender, meaning non-male genders, often underrepresented in community energy projects.

- Level of community participation

Cases had to entail the collective active participation of vulnerable citizens (in various degrees, i.e. low to high). As highlighted in the adopted definition, the active involvement of citizens is a paramount feature for selection. The project might have been initiated by municipalities, NGOs or any other third-

sector organisation concerned with alleviating energy poverty. Still, vulnerable citizens must have been actively participating and not being mere recipients of actions carried out by other subjects.

- Energy poverty reduction

Cases were included that designed and/or implemented actions to reduce energy costs and, thereby, energy poverty, specifically falling into the following categories:

- a. Successfully established community energy communities (ECs)
 - i. deliberately addressing the aim of reducing energy poverty or
 - ii. not designed to address energy poverty, but delivered results to reduce energy poverty.
- b. ECs in the making: community energy projects that were at the early developmental stage.
- c. Unsuccessful ECs
 - i. projects that did not take off
 - ii. projects that did not achieve energy poverty results (yet).

1.4 Case study selection and access

After multiple meetings and calls with different energy communities' organisers, we selected two cases in Norway, two in Denmark and three in Italy. Further, Austria was also targeted for case selection and data collection; however, relevant cases were not identified (details on this process can be found in Appendix B).

1.4.1 Sofienberggata 7 - Norway

This case regards the renovations and energy upgrade of an apartment building at Sofienberggata 7, in Oslo. The municipally owned housing block on Sofienberggata underwent significant refurbishment, including a complete energy overhaul with new highly insulated facades, an updated ventilation system, thermal energy wells, and solar energy collection on both the roof and the facades (Futurebuilt, 2023). (pictures 1 and 2).

These measures aimed to cut the building's energy consumption by more than 70 per cent. The residents of the newly refurbished building will benefit from these changes through reduced electricity bills. Better lighting at entrances and in the passage to Markveien will contribute to safety and well-being in the backyard.

Charging stations for electric bicycles and cars have also been installed in the garage.

Picture 1. Solar panels on the roof,
© Pariman Boostani, December 2023

Picture 2. Solar panels on the facade, © Pariman Boostani, Dec 2023

Funding: The municipality funds this project and owns all the buildings. ENOVA¹ has also provided financial support (350 272 NOK ≈ €30,459).

Vulnerability criteria: Residents are low-income groups and, in some instances, belong to ethnic minority groups, are of old age, and are disabled (mentally and physically).

Community participation in the project: At the initial stages of the energy project, community members attended a meeting where the project plan and timeline were introduced. Following this, letters were sent out to keep residents informed about developments and which buildings would be renovated. Several meetings and open discussions were held throughout the project, allowing residents to voice concerns, share their needs and provide input on the renovations. In some cases, their feedback influenced aspects of the renovation process. During the apartment renovations, depending on the scope of work, residents were temporarily relocated to hotels at no extra cost, with the project covering all expenses beyond their usual rent.

1.4.2 Bergen ecovillage – Norway

Bergen Ecovillage (BØL) is located on Osterøy. The village is currently in an early development stage, meaning that only a single home has been built so far, and aims to offer opportunities to develop local, sustainable businesses and activities such as ecotourism and food production (picture 3). The village will be divided into seven yards and will have 39 homes: detached houses, terraced houses, apartment houses, dormitories and communal houses. These houses will be built from environmentally friendly, sustainable, and local materials. This area will follow environmentally friendly energy solutions, and the terraced houses will have natural ventilation (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2019).

The homes will be low-energy homes or plus houses and nearly CO2-neutral. The homes will be built from wood and wood-based materials (picture 4). The houses' electricity meters are supposed to record both consumption and production. Own measurement and monitoring of power consumption has shown to be effective for savings (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2019). The

Picture 4. Growing local food with the help of community members, taken by Bergen Ecovillage

main electricity supply will be from the electricity grid, supplemented by solar cells mounted on the buildings. Roof-mounted flat solar collectors that work well in fair weather can be combined with vacuum tube solar collectors that work well in cloudy and cold weather (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2019). The system can be supplied with

Picture 3. Architectural model of Bergen ecovillage, taken by Bergen Ecovillage.

¹ Enova is working for Norway's transition to a low-emission society. The transition requires that the people together succeed in cutting greenhouse gas emissions and creating new values, through innovation and technological development. Therefore, Enova works to ensure that new energy and climate technology is developed and used in the market. Enova SF is located in Trondheim and has approximately 110 employees. The company is owned by the Ministry of Climate and Environment. more information on <https://www.enova.no/>

heat from wood ovens and wood-burning stoves in the cold season. The place has good sunny conditions and abundant access to firewood, in combination with electricity from the landline and solar collectors and/or solar cells, which is a safe and flexible choice (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2019).

Funding: Ledaal Eiendom (LE) AS is a project manager and will assist BØL with the development, planning and engineering/ framework application for the homes. (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2019, 2022). The initial capital contributed by BØL and individuals was NOK 2.2 million (equal to 191,304 EUR) (1.2 million (104,348 EUR) in cash, 1 million (€86,950) invested in road construction and site preparation) (Bergen Økologiske Landsby, 2022). They also applied for housing banking and ENOVA (Ledaal Eiendom AS & Bergen Økologiske Landsby SA, 2022).

Vulnerability criteria: Several prospective members cannot afford to build these houses as they are living on a low income. Thus, they are working on funding applications to ENOVA and private and public institutions. Also, women and older people play an essential role in this eco-village project. A woman is one of the project leaders, and two older women are active board members in the ecovillage.

Community participation in the project: A woman and a man are currently the leaders of this project. They define themselves as vulnerable. However, they have asked other people to join their project. They have also held meetings and dinner parties with volunteers interested in joining. People can speak their minds at those meetings while the project leaders present their plans.

1.4.3 Solhuset (Energifællesskab Avedøre)- Denmark

Store Hus, also known as Large House, is an example of how a consumer-owned utility company (Avedøre District Heating A.M.B.A), and the tenants in a social housing can create a sustained environmental change (Ebo Consult, 2024). Energifællesskab Avedøre is a broader community energy initiative covering a larger area, including Solhuset and surrounding institutions and neighbourhoods. The Energy Community Avedøre A.M.B.A was established on 18 August 2020. The founders are "Hvidovre Municipality, Hvidovre Gymnasium, Avedøre Landsbylaug, Avedøre District Heating A.M.B.A., Filmbyen and EBO Consult" (EBO Consult, 2020). The parties managed to establish 60 solar panels on the roof of Solhuset, with an area of about 750 m² and 160 polycrystalline solar cell panels on the south facade of the house (Picture 5 and 6).

Picture 5. South facade of the house, © Pariman Boostani, February 2024.

Picture 6. Solhuset building, taken by Pariman Boostani, February 2024.

The solar panels provide around 350 MWh of energy yearly, fulfilling 75-100% of the hot water usage for the 454 apartments in Solhuset from April to September. The idea of transitioning from "Store Hus" to "Solhuset" was developed by the former vice-chairman of Avedøre district heating company, in partnership with the district heating company's administrator, EBO Consult (Ebo Consult, 2024).

Founder: Hvidovre Municipality, Hvidovre Gymnasium, Avedøre Landsbylaug, Avedøre District Heating A.M.B.A., Filmbyen and EBO Consult A/S (as secretariat and administrator for the energy community)

Vulnerability criteria: Low-income tenants and immigrants are living in this building.

Community participation in the project: The residents are represented on the board and have the right to vote on every decision made by the community of residents. Residents are active in different projects (such as repairing cafes and recycling workshops). They elected their board members for their community, and they have the right to vote on every decision made in their community. This also helped community members have an active role in the energy community ².

1.4.4 Universitetets Energifællesskab (UEF) – Denmark

The city of Aarhus and Aarhus University (AU) have set ambitious climate goals. If these goals are to succeed, citizens need to be involved and play an active role. The AURORA initiative provides such opportunities for citizens in Aarhus, especially students and staff at AU, to participate in the green transition. The energy community (Universitetets Energifællesskab, UEs) in Aarhus has been officially registered with the Danish Business Authority since September 2023³. Therefore, it has its own legal identity independent from the EU H2020 project AURORA⁴. At the demo site in Aarhus, they established the energy community (energifællesskab) by crowdfunding the installation of rooftop solar photovoltaic panels on campus (Picture 7). The community is a solar cooperative (solcellelaug) following the Danish spirit of andelstanken⁵. In addition to annual economic returns, community members can access energy-related public discussions and hands-on workshops in the community.

Picture 7. Solar panels on the roof campus, taken by UEF members, 2024.

Funding: The energy community is set up as a solar cooperative (Universitetets Energifællesskab F.M.B.A or UEF), which owns the rooftop solar installation. The cooperative sells the electricity produced by the solar installation to Aarhus University at a fixed price, and members of UEF get economic returns every year. Since it is a cooperative, citizens in Aarhus, especially students and staff at AU, can buy one or more shares and become co-owners. Every year, based on the shares they own, they get economic returns⁶.

Vulnerability criteria: The AURORA project (which laid the background work for establishing the energy community UEF) intends to address energy poverty. However, the 'vulnerability' is less evident in the Aarhus demonstration site than in other demonstration sites. Nevertheless, students are a vulnerable group since the vast majority of them live on a tight budget, do not have a stable income or savings to invest in and have very limited access to credit. Further, the project focuses on involving students who do not own a house and do not have enough money to make significant investments. By setting a meagre cost for the shares of the cooperative, students are enabled to participate in the project. Other individuals, like university staff, can join this project. However, this project's vulnerability profile has targeted low-income students and researchers who can buy a share at an affordable price through crowdfunding.

² . <https://eboconsult.dk/en/2020/06/08/denmarks-first-energy-community/>

³ .<https://www.uef.dk/>

⁴ .<https://www.aurora-h2020.eu/>

⁵ .<https://www.uef.dk/about-us>

⁶ .<https://www.uef.dk/>

Community participation in the project: Citizens in Aarhus can become members of UEF by buying shares in the crowdfunded solar installation. In addition to annual economic returns, citizens can access energy-related public discussions and hands-on workshops in the community. This project has a practice of holding numerous meetings, discussions and workshops with community members to raise their awareness about the energy crisis. Community members are active in the project as they can participate in project decision-making.

1.4.5 Rome – Municipality VII – “A Otto Minuti dal Sole” (Eight Minutes from the Sun) – Italy

‘A Otto Minuti dal Sole’ (meaning “Eight Minutes from the Sun”) is a renewable, energy solidarity community (ESC) with a strong social and community matrix. It is an energy community that aims to make citizens no longer just energy consumers but prosumers, i.e., producers of energy to directly satisfy their primary energy needs. There is a strong intent to influence cultural change regarding energy consumption. This ESC does not yet have a photovoltaic system. The functional feasibility study for its installation was carried out in summer 2023.

Funding: The energy community is an association that brings together 23 families from the Rome neighbourhoods Tor Fiscale and Alessandrino, two commercial activities in the area and the ‘Casa di Cristian’ community (within the local parish). So far, it has been financed by its members (expenditure at this stage was minimal), as well as by 5,000 Euros from the Lazio Region for the implementation of the feasibility study.

Vulnerability criteria ‘A Otto Minuti dal Sole’ is a community that also involves (but not only) vulnerable low-income families in the neighbourhoods of Tor Fiscale and Alessandrino. Furthermore, associates in the ESC are in better economic conditions. Since its inception, this has been an energy and solidarity community aiming to alleviate energy poverty (and Tor Fiscale and Alessandrino are marginalised neighbourhoods).

Community participation in the project: All the 23 involved families are full members of the ESC (as well as the 2 micro-entrepreneurs and ‘Casa di Cristian’) with deliberative power. Regular meetings are held among members. The President of the ESC is the engineer who inspired the birth of the community.

1.4.6 Rome – Municipality I – “Le Vele” – Italy

“Le Vele” energy and solidarity community was established at the end of 2022 at the Vaccari Institute which deals with psycho-physical rehabilitation and educational and social integration of disabled people. In November 2023, a 90-kW solar PV system was installed, which produces approximately 120,000 kWh of clean energy per year.

Funding: The Community's photovoltaic system was donated by the Banco dell'Energia Foundation, thanks to a donation that Banco dell'Energia got from the electricity company Edison Energia, which also ensures free of charge (and indefinitely) the maintenance of the system. Edison also renewed, free of charge, the electrical system of the Vaccari Institute (where the photovoltaic system is located), which was not in order.

Vulnerability criteria: The Vaccari Institute's users are people with disabilities. Furthermore, with the support of the Parents' Association of disabled people, some vulnerable families living nearby, in a near future, should be able to receive the excess energy produced. Additionally, with the savings

obtained and the proceeds of the incentives, social interventions aimed at people in energy poverty will be financed.

Community participation in the project: The Association of parents of disabled people, assisted by the Vaccari Institute, has been a member of the ESC since its establishment and has participated and actively participates in the entire process. Vulnerable families who should soon be involved will also become members of the ESC. Members of the ESC are also the Vaccari Institute, the non-profit 'Scenario B' (an association involved with energy transition issues, providing assistance to the energy community, particularly on regulatory and technical matters), the Municipality I and the Banco dell'Energia Foundation. The ESC holds regular meetings among members. The staff of the Vaccari Institute and the disabled people who attend it are not members of the ESC. However, initiatives are taking place to involve them in and to inform them about the ESC.

1.4.7 San Nicola da Crissa – Critaro – Italy

It is the first Renewable and Solidarity Energy Community in Calabria. The project was developed and implemented by '3E Environment Energy Economy' (an Italian SME working in the installation of photovoltaic plants) with a 66.80 kW photovoltaic system and a 36-kWh storage tank, which is now connected to the grid and fully operational. The energy community is not only implementing renewables but it is also socially supportive, because it is projected to significantly reduce the bills of families in energy poverty (living in social housing). The system will power the school's utilities on which the photovoltaic system is installed and will share the remaining energy fed into the grid with the 30 families of the community. The community was inaugurated in January 2023.

Funding: The energy community is an association that includes 30 families living in social housing in the Municipality of San Nicola da Crissa. The financing was obtained thanks to the stipulation of a mortgage (at a subsidised rate without the granting of real guarantees) with the Banco di Credito Cooperativo. The loan will be repaid in 15 years thanks to the revenues of the ESC.

Vulnerability criteria: As already stated, 'Critaro' is a community involving all (and only) families of San Nicola da Crissa living in social housing. Most of them are disadvantaged families. Since its inception, this is an energy and solidarity community with the specific aim of alleviating energy poverty.

Community participation in the project: All 30 involved families, as well as the Municipality of San Nicola da Crissa, are full members of the ESC with deliberative power. Regular meetings are held among members. The Mayor of San Nicola da Crissa is the president of the ESC.

1.5. Recruitment procedures

Following the Plan for RL3, all subjects identified in the cases selected were potentially considered for inclusion, but priority was given to three categories of respondents:

- Vulnerable individuals involved in the project
- Leaders/organisers
- Local authority officers, if they had meaningful interaction with the case study project

1.5.1 Gender+ intersectional criteria

We aimed to involve more women in our recruitment process for interviews in Norway, Italy and Denmark, the reason being that women are often less well represented and involved in energy community projects (Cunha et al., 2021; Tsagkari, 2022). We found it an added value to consider women's viewpoints and discuss their challenges and motivations for participating in the EC's projects. By doing so, we attempted to gain different perspectives on sustainable energy and sustainable living, allowing for a comparative analysis of gender approaches to community energy projects and the issue of energy poverty.

Gender differences are evident in women's understanding of energy issues and their level of participation in meetings and discussions (Köhlin et al., 2011). Their perspective on their community can help identify the enablers and hindrances to their involvement in community energy projects. A society's social, cultural, economic and political context can influence women's participation in community energy projects. Therefore, we drafted a guide named RL3² to assist the RL3 researchers in the fieldwork at developing or integrating a gender perspective. This aimed to help understand how interview questions could gather different gender perspectives. To examine gender differences in power distribution within energy communities, we inquired about participants' primary roles in these initiatives. Additionally, we explored perspectives on energy pricing to assess the extent to which gender disparities influence outcomes and behavioural changes in energy consumption. Our inquiry targeted various factors, including time availability, financial resources, knowledge, awareness, sense of belonging and community engagement, to determine whether gendered differences manifest in responses. By doing so, we aimed to gain deeper insights into the structural and behavioural dimensions shaping gendered participation in energy communities.

2. Methodology and study materials

2.1 Choice of the method

Several methods were implemented to analyse behavioural changes at individual and collective levels and the role of vulnerable groups and individuals in energy communities. The methods are as follows:

- **Desk research**

- Reviewing cases database D2.2 for suitability of inclusion

We started with documentary research where possible cases that met the criteria for energy communities were identified. Information about the cases was identified and contacted via e-mail at this stage. After informing the project participants about the study's goal, we got acquainted with their project's goal, inclusion criteria, level of people participation, etc., to see whether they could be selected for further research.

- Two cases, "A Otto Minuti dal Sole" and La Vele, were identified through participation in a coordination committee of the Rome and Lazio RESCs. Participants were contacted, meetings were set up, and the study was explained through in-person meetings.
- Searching for web information regarding cases suitable for inclusion
- Once a case was selected, all the available material on the web and from scientific and grey literature was collected, further the organisers were solicited to send any relevant material.

- Several online meetings were held with researchers, local authorities and research projects related to energy communities to get more information about possible cases to contact.

- **Interviews**

- Semi-structured individual interviews:

Data from all participants were collected through semi-structured interviews. Three interview questionnaires were developed to gather information targeting the three target groups: vulnerable individuals, project leaders, and local authorities. The questionnaire targeting vulnerable individuals focused on their living experiences, challenges in joining energy communities, motivations for joining the project, possible behavioural changes by participating in energy communities and/or learning new energy-saving approaches and energy consumption behaviours.

Regarding the project leaders' questionnaire, we tried to cover different aspects, including their motivations for establishing the project, their role in the project, identification and roles of stakeholders involved in the projects, challenges they faced before, during, and after the project implementation, plans to engage community members and more specifically vulnerable groups in decision-making, regulation and national policies (e.g. specific national laws that facilitated/hindered their development, national laws about energy production threshold), energy poverty and vulnerability actions (e.g. actions to engage vulnerable groups in their energy communities, affordable energy prices, a supportive financial plan for vulnerable groups to be part of the energy community or pay their energy bills), as well as pro-environmental behaviours (e.g. whether they have any workshops or training sessions for community members about sustainable energy consumption, plans to awareness raising regarding climate change and sustainable energy behaviour).

Finally, in the questionnaire for local authorities, we covered their role in the project, strategies to engage vulnerable groups in energy communities, challenges faced by local authorities to support energy projects, energy poverty and energy education, and existing and potential policies to facilitate energy project development and increase public participation.

- **Research workshops**

On the 4th of September 2024, a workshop was conducted with stakeholders of the energy community cases targeted in Norway, Denmark and Italy. The goal was to present findings from the Danish, Italian, and Norwegian cases and experiences of stakeholders involved in energy communities to facilitate the exchange of best practices and common reflection on the studies' findings. After the presentations, a general discussion was conducted, and both barriers and benefits towards behavioural change and ECs' development, identified through the fieldwork, were discussed (Please check the 4.9 section for more information).

- **Observational methods**

Site visiting: We took pictures and notes related to site visits and events held by the energy communities. The aim of site visits was to document and understand how energy communities function. By taking pictures and notes during visits, we captured important aspects of community engagement, infrastructure, and activities. This helped us see how people participate, what challenges they face, and how the community is organised. The visual documentation also supported our analysis and provided extra insights beyond interviews and observations.

2.2 Study material

2.2.1 Data collection and harmonisation

Data were collected using semi-structured interviews following the questionnaire provided by the NTNU team to the Italian and Austrian teams. The NTNU Team created all questionnaires based on the guidelines elaborated earlier in the interview guide, which were agreed upon with RL3 partners. After completing the questionnaire drafts, all teams were invited to comment and provide suggestions to harmonise the document and make it accessible to all RL3 participating countries. This step ensured the ability of all teams to agree on the utility and understanding of the finished questionnaire. This allowed the methodological approaches to be identical and ensured comparability between countries.

Each researcher in the RL3 countries was trusted to ensure that gender differences, stereotypes, and potential biases were investigated thoroughly. They were best placed to understand local cultures and the intricacies and context of the interviewee's language and social dynamics. Their familiarity with cultural norms allowed them to conduct the research in an informed way, ensuring that the findings accurately reflected the interviewees' perspectives and experiences. In addition, regular RL3 meetings were held to discuss possible issues during the interviewing phase.

2.3 Ethical procedures

Before conducting the interviews, we sent the project leaders an electronic letter of intent to read and, if they agreed on the procedure, sign. That document introduced ACCTING's plan for the interviews and site visits and provided information on data treatment. Furthermore, confidentiality was ensured by removing sensitive data and any data that could lead to recognising a person for the data analysis.

During the recruitment process, s (See Appendix D) for participants were sent for signing to individuals to familiarise them with the procedure and their rights during and after the interviews, data protection, anonymity and confidentiality, possible risks and disadvantages, benefits of joining the project, and some specific information about the ACCTING project, such as the project results, funding, and analysis procedure.

Moreover, based on an agreement between NTNU and the Data Protection Services of SIKT – the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research SIKT assessed that the processing of personal data in this project meets the requirements of data protection legislation.

Several online meetings and calls were held throughout the project to foster trust between project leaders and ACCTING members. The goals of ACCTING and our specific research requirements were outlined during the first meetings with project leaders. The following communication exchange was aimed at ensuring a clear understanding of the research objectives. The research team kept them updated on the project's progress through regular email correspondence and arranged follow-up meetings to address inquiries and further clarify the project's content.

Regarding building trust between the researcher and participants, we followed an introductory discussion before each interview to introduce the researcher and the field of expertise, how the data would be collected, and what topics would be discussed during the interview. It should be noted that during the online interviews, the procedure was the same; however, we presented some slides before the interviews to talk about ACCTING aims and goals of RL3.

Analysis and Results

3. Data collected and analysis

3.1 Steps and Timeframe

Case study A – Sofienberggata 7

The case study selection process was the same for all Norwegian and Danish case studies in this research line. We identified this case study through an online search, emailed the project leader, and invited him to an online meeting on Teams. We had the first online meeting in November 2023, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about Sofienberggata 7. We did the first round of interviews in December 2023. In the first round, we interviewed five individuals, including the project leader. The second round of interviews was conducted in May 2024, and four more interviews were conducted.

Case study B – Bergen ecovillage

We had the first online meeting in September 2023, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about Bergen Ecovillage. Then, we sent the letter of intent to them, and following this, they requested another online meeting to get more clarification on some parts of the letter of intent. After they agreed to collaborate with the ACCTING project, we did five in-person interviews in February 2024. Then, two online interviews were conducted in March 2024 with a representative from the local authority and one of the community members.

Case study C – Energifællesskab Avedøre (Solhuset)

We had the first online meeting in January 2024, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about their project. We also sent the letter of intent to him, and after he agreed to collaborate with the ACCTING project, we did all the interviews in February 2024. We interviewed five individuals, including the project leader.

Case study D – Universitetets Energifællesskab (UEF)

We had the first online meeting in January 2024, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about UEF. We also sent them the letter of intent, and after they agreed to collaborate with the ACCTING project, we did eight in-person and two online interviews in January 2024. Then, three online interviews were done with two community members in June 2024.

Case study E – “A Otto Minuti dal Sole”

We identified this case study through our participation in the coordination committee of the Rome and Lazio RESCs. We had the first in-person meeting in February 2024, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about this ESC. The President of the ESC showed great interest in ACCTING's approach and enthusiastically joined the project. We did all the interviews between the end of February and the beginning of April 2024.

Case study F – Le Vele

We identified this case through our participation in the coordination committee of the Rome and Lazio RESCs and having been informed about the inauguration ceremony of the photovoltaic system

installed on the roof of the Vaccari Institute. We contacted, first, the leader of the Association Scenario B, who then, facilitated the contact with the President of the ESC, who is also the president of the Vaccari Institute. We had the first in-person meeting with both in February 2024, during which we discussed our project and received useful information about this ESC. Both showed an interest in ACCTING's approach and joined the interview process. We did all the interviews between the end of February and May 2024.

Case study G – CRITARO

We identified this case through our initial documentary research. Then, the mayor of San Nicola da Crissa was contacted through mutual acquaintances who facilitated the liaison. The first meeting (online) was in July 2023 followed by many other meetings. The interest in ACCTING was genuine, but adherence to the project timeline and requests was much less enthusiastic than in the previously described cases. We did all the interviews between the end of April and mid-August 2024.

3.2 Interviewee recruitment procedures

Table 1 shows a summary of the recruitment procedure and their vulnerability profile.

Case study A – Sofienberggata 7

The project leader helped us recruit community members; he contacted them in person and let us know who was available for interviews. The participants signed the informed consent form during the interviews, and then we conducted the interviews with them. Because of the language issue we had during the interviews, the project leaders were present during all the interviews and helped us with translation when needed. Despite his presence in the interviews, it was perceived that participants felt free to express their opinions about the project because they communicated well with the project leader. We reached nine individuals for this case study as follows:

- Project leader: one individual
- Community members: eight members (including immigrants, disabled groups, women, and old people)
- Local authority: In this project, the project leader also works in Oslo municipality. We could not find another person as he has not responded to the e-mails.

Case study B – Bergen ecovillage

One of the project leaders helped us recruit community members; she contacted them in person and let us know who was available for interviews. Moreover, one of the interviews with a community member was in Norwegian and English. There was also one online interview with one of the community members, as he was unavailable during our stay in Bergen. Overall, we reached seven individuals for this case study as follows:

- Project leaders: three individuals
- Community members: three members (including immigrants, women, and low-income families)
- Local authority: one person from Østerøy municipality.

Case study C – Energifællesskab Avedøre (Solhuset)

One of the board members helped us recruit community members; she contacted them in person and let us know who was available for interviews. Overall, we reached five individuals for this case study as follows:

- Project leader: four individuals (three of them were also tenants)
- Community members: one individual
- Local authority: They had no collaboration with the municipality and did not mention any names to contact.

Case study D – Universitetets Energifællesskab (UEF)

One of the project leaders helped us recruit community members. She contacted them in person and let us know who was available for interviews. Overall, we reached twelve individuals for this case study as follows:

- Project leaders: four individuals
- Community members: seven members (including women and low-income individuals)
- Local authority: one person from Aarhus municipality, The President of Energy Communities in Denmark

Case study E – “A Otto Minuti dal Sole”

We interviewed 10 individuals:

- The President of the ESC (man, in person)
- The President of the Association “Casa di Cristian” (man, in person)
- The Councillor for the Environment, Waste and Agribusiness Affairs – Rome Municipality VII (woman, in person)
- The Tor Fiscale Parish priest (man, in person)
- Six citizens associated to the ESC (4 women and 2 men; 4 in-person and 2 online; among them, 2 people in severe economic difficulties and 2 retired very elderly people).

The ESC’s President helped identify and facilitate the contact of most of the interviewees. Two citizens were directly interviewed during a dinner organised by the Casa di Cristian.

Case study F – Le Vele

We did 9 interviews:

- The President of the ESC, who is also President of the Vaccari Institute (woman, in person)
- The Councillor for the Environment and Energy – Rome Municipality I (man, online)
- One representative of Scenario B (woman, online)
- One representative of Banco dell’Energia (woman, online)
- A group interview with 3 representatives of Edison Energia (2 women and 1 man, online)
- 3 members of the Parents’ association of disabled people in the Vaccari Institute (parents of people with strong disabilities with a need for permanent assistance; one is a woman in

severe economic difficulties; and the two others are old men in good economic conditions, all online interviews)

- One staff member of the Vaccari Institute (man, online)

Scenario B helped in the identification and in the facilitation of the contact of most the interviewees. The others were identified and contacted thanks to a snow-ball procedure.

Case study G – CRITARO

While no difficulty was encountered in interviewing the mayor himself and the person in charge of the photovoltaic system (“3E Environment Energy Economy”), it was much more difficult to succeed in interviewing the citizens living in the public housing of the ESC.

We interviewed 4 individuals:

- The President of the ESC, Mayor of San Nicola da Crissa (man, online)
- The Vice-President of “3E Environment Energy Economy” (man, online)
- 2 citizens (2 women living in the social housing in San Nicola da Crissa)

People interviewed were identified and selected thanks to the help of the mayor.

Table 1. Summary of the selection cases

Case study	country	Timeframe	No. of interviews	Interviewee profile
Sofienberggata 7	Norway	Nov 2023-May 2024	9	Project leader, 8 community members (immigrants, disabled, women, elderly), local authority (project leader also municipal staff)
Bergen Ecovillage	Norway	Sep 2023-Mar 2024	7	3 project leaders, 3 community members (immigrants, women, low-income), 1 local authority
Energifællesskab Avedøre (Solhuset)	Denmark	Jan 2024-Feb 2024	5	4 project leaders (3 also tenants), 1 community member, no local authority involvement
UEF (Universitetets Energifællesskab)	Denmark	Jan 2024-Jun 2024	13	4 project leaders, 7 community members (women, low-income), 2 local authority
A Otto Minuti dal Sole	Italy	Feb 2024-Apr 2024	10	ESC President, Association leader, councillor, parish priest, 6 citizens (incl. economically disadvantaged and elderly)
Le Vele	Italy	Feb 2024-May 2024	9	The President of the ESC, The Councillor for the Environment and Energy, 2 women, 2 men, 3 disable,

CRITARO	Italy	Jul 2023-Aug 2024	4	Mayor (ESC President), Vice-President of 3E, 2 women in social housing
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3.3 Sample statistics

3.3.1. Main vulnerability criteria in the target groups

Figure 1 shows that socioeconomic status is the main vulnerability criterion within the three countries. Most of the people affected were from low-income groups who could not afford to pay their energy bills or were unemployed and received financial support from the government. While the project leaders and policymakers were generally considered not to be in any condition of inequality, there were some cases where they were also vulnerable and fell into other categories (e.g., health conditions, housing conditions, migration status).

Figure 1. Main vulnerability criteria in three target groups.

3.3.2. Gender + Intersectional Perspectives

In RLC2-RL3, we interviewed 30 women and 27 men. All 57 participants identified themselves as either men or women, and we did not encounter individuals of other genders. Since we have considered gender a vulnerability criterion in RL3, we tried to recruit more women for the energy community projects to ensure their voices were heard (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Gender + intersectional perspective.

3.3.3. Gender + Intersectional Perspectives and their roles in Energy Communities

Case study A – Sofienberggata 7

During the first online meeting with the project leader, we presented the criteria for individual recruitment, and he was aware of the vulnerability criteria for the ACCTING project. We asked him to invite the following people to the interview:

- Single mothers
- Women, especially old women
- Disabled female individuals (if it is possible) or women with health conditions
- Women with a migration background
- Women who have a low income

Moreover, in the second round of interviews, we asked the project leader to invite only women to the interviews. Finally, we could interview more women than men (5 in total). Their vulnerability criteria can be seen as follows:

- Woman 1: Migration background, single mother, low-income family
- Woman 2: old woman, retired, living alone
- Woman 3: woman with a disability, unemployed
- Woman 4: migration background, taking care of her disabled child, low-income family
- Woman 5: low-income family

Critical reflection of strengths and shortcomings:

- Because we could not use random selection following the snowball methodology, the results cannot represent the population living in this area.

- We followed snowball sampling, and there will be sampling bias. Therefore, it may affect the results of the analysis (this can be seen in all the following case studies).
- We invited individuals with migration backgrounds. We also tried to follow Norwegian and English in the interviews for those comfortable with the Norwegian language. However, two individuals with migration backgrounds could speak fluently in neither of the two languages, so we could not get their whole opinion on the project.
- Those who were from a low-income family preferred not to mention it explicitly. However, the results of some of their answers showed that they are economically vulnerable.

Case study B – Bergen ecovillage

During the first online meeting with the project leaders, we presented the criteria for individual recruitment, and they were aware of the vulnerability criteria for the ACCTING project. As mentioned in the previous section, it was difficult to identify individuals for this community as the project is still in its initial stages. Therefore, out of three interested individuals living in this ecovillage, two of them were female based on the following criteria:

- Woman 1: low-income family
- Woman 2: old woman, retired, living alone in the countryside

Critical reflection of strengths and shortcomings:

- Those who were from a low-income family preferred not to mention it explicitly. However, the results of some of their answers showed that they are economically vulnerable.

Case study C – Energifællesskab Avedøre (Solhuset)

During the email contacts with the project leader, we presented the criteria for individual recruitment, and he was aware of the vulnerability criteria for the ACCTING project. However, the tenants' recruitment process was challenging for them, and they could only invite one tenant as a vulnerable person. However, three of the board members were tenants as well, so during the interviews, we covered some questions from the vulnerable group interview guide to ask them.

- Woman 1: board member and tenant, also mentioned her physical disability during the interview
- Woman 2: old woman, disability profile, low-income

Critical reflection of strengths and shortcomings:

- Those who were from a low-income family preferred not to mention it explicitly. However, the results of some of their answers showed that they are economically vulnerable.

Case study D – Universitetets Energifællesskab (UEF)

During the first online meeting with the project leaders, we presented the criteria for individual recruitment, and they were aware of the vulnerability criteria for the ACCTING project. As mentioned in the previous section, it was difficult to identify individuals for this community as the project is still in its initial stages. Therefore, out of ten individuals, four were female based on the following criteria:

- Woman 1: she wanted to promote women's empowerment in such projects
- Woman 2: student, low-income
- Woman 3: project leader

- Woman 4: project leader

Critical reflection of strengths and shortcomings:

- The project is in the initial stages. Therefore, it was challenging for the project leader to identify more women or students as vulnerable individuals.
- Those who were from a low-income family preferred not to mention it explicitly. However, the results of some of their answers showed that they are economically vulnerable.

Case study E –“A Otto Minuti dal Sole”

As already stated, of the six citizens interviewed, 4 are women. Of these 4 women, 1 is in serious economic difficulty and 1 is an elderly pensioner. Of the 2 men, 1 is a former micro-entrepreneur who went bankrupt due to the restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 epidemic and 1 is a very old person. Overall, of the 10 people interviewed, 5 are women and 5 men.

Case study F – Le Vele

The 3 members of the parents’ association interviewed all live in a distressed condition because they have to care for their disabled family members. In addition, two are very old men and the third is a woman who lives in very precarious economic conditions. Overall, of the 11 people involved in the interviews, 6 are women and 5 men.

Case study G - CRITARO

Both women interviewed in San Nicola da Crissa are living in social housing and their families meet socio-economic difficulties.

According to Table 2, most women were community members, while men were mainly the project leaders of these energy communities. This shows that in these energy communities, men mostly took leadership roles and were more active in projects, while women were seen as members of the communities. However, in some cases, women were also the project leaders, such as in the Bergen ecovillage and the UEF project.

Table 2. Gender and their roles in Energy Communities.

Gender	Role in the community	Number of participants
women	Community member	20
	Project leader	9
	Local authority	1
Men	Community member	11
	Project leader	13
	Local authority	3

3.3.4. Comparability of the cases

LGBTQI+ individuals were not included in any of the cases, which might be a result of several reasons, such as their lack of participation due to discrimination, a reluctance to self-identify as part of that community, or, most likely, the low number of individuals involved in the energy communities investigated.

All cases, independent of the country, were run by people sensitive to environmental sustainability and energy cost reduction. This was true for both the vulnerable groups and project leaders. In some cases, such as in Italy, the policymakers were involved in the ECs to a larger degree and took a more direct approach. There was a discrepancy between how far the energy communities had developed. Bergen Ecovillage had just started and has therefore not yet been able to reduce energy costs for the members, while, e.g., La Vele had installed PV systems in November of 2023, which produce 120.000 kWh per year. It is important to be cognizant of such differences when evaluating the results and interpreting outcomes and policy measures.

4. Results

4.1 Behavioural change at the individual and collective levels in vulnerable groups

In the following paragraphs, variables affecting behaviours at the individual and collective levels are presented in the context of the cases researched.

In Sofienberggata 7 in Norway, the majority of residents were vulnerable, and they did not have enough knowledge on how to live sustainably compared to other cases in Denmark and Italy. However, they tried to save more energy because of the energy prices, which indicates sustainable behavioural practices towards energy consumption driven by economic reasons. For example, an individual mentioned her concern about high energy prices and how she changed her behaviour to have fewer energy bills at the end of the month. She said:

"I save electricity by dressing a little more in the winter instead of turning on the stove" (NO-VL07⁷).

Another vulnerable individual tried to save energy by turning off the lights and following sustainable energy consumption behaviour by changing her daily habits to save more energy and reduce energy bills. She said:

"At home, we turn off the light, wash clothes rarely, and do not turn on the water when we take a shower. We must learn that other people also need water and then spend a little, so we have to do economics at home. That can change me" (NO-VL06).

Similarly, another vulnerable individual mentioned:

"Nowadays, I am very careful not to use much electricity, so I pay the lowest. I never turn on the heater when it is not needed. I do not wash my clothes daily, maybe two times a week. I try to wash dishes by hand instead of using the washing machine. So I do not get high electricity...I always tell my kids to wear more clothes, socks, and a sweater, and if necessary, we can turn on the heater because I want to ensure that the bills are the lowest so I can have some money" (NO-VL05).

They also tried to use reusable items instead of buying new ones. Interviewees also mentioned that this project helped them to connect with others because of the renovated meeting hall, which indicates socially inclusive outcomes that these projects might generate. They could participate in various

⁷ . The abbreviation is based on (the country (Norway(NO), Denmark(DK), Italy(IT)- Interviewee profile (vulnerable (vl), project leader (pl), policy stakeholder (p) – code of the interview)

workshops and meetings, which allowed them to support each other when needed. Additionally, they received brochures on how to recycle garbage and made efforts to follow the instructions.

In Bergen Ecovillage, it should be noted that this project has yet to take off because of the financial challenges; therefore, we cannot discuss its activities, results and impact on sustainability. However, they have had different meetings with people interested in joining the project. They also tried to have workshops on growing local food and invited interested individuals to join the workshops and training sessions. The community members were interested in following pro-environmental behaviour. For example, an old woman mentioned her concern about preserving nature as follows:

"Instead of constructing roads and buildings, we should grow food and normally use these lands for food. We should work with nature and not against it. That is my opinion. That is why I want to live in an eco-village. I like this lifestyle" (NO-VL09).

Another woman shared her experience about participating in the permaculture course, learning to grow local food, and following sustainable energy-saving practices. She said:

"I passed several courses in permaculture, and also, I guess, some energy efficiency courses at the university where we had some subjects within energy efficiency and decentralised water systems" (NO-VL10).

After interviewing current community members, they found that their motivations to join this project were mainly influenced by their life experiences and knowledge of sustainable lifestyles. The project organised permaculture workshops to teach community members how to grow local foods. People gathered, met and built social ties while learning to grow local foods.

In the Danish cases, most people interviewed were aware of the energy crisis and environmental issues before joining the projects. Their life experiences sustainably directed their energy consumption. For instance, in the Solhuset project, the board members were the tenants who would like to insulate the buildings to save more energy. One of the board members also talked about using solar panels to produce local energy to save energy and reduce energy costs. She mentioned:

"The energy that you pull down is free and does not make the environment worse or pollute our air or something... So I think it is the right thing to do. I am surprised we did not do that 20 years ago" (DK-VL01).

She also talked about meetings regarding energy and climate change in this energy community and how they helped community members to be more involved in these topics by participating in the discussions, sharing their ideas and expressing their concerns. It should be highlighted that the maintenance of solar panels can cause a financial burden to this community, and they tried to share their fears in their meetings to see what residents suggest and how they can tackle the economic challenges. She noted:

"Everybody does (speak about energy prices) in the country because it becomes so expensive. We have several groups we are working on about everything here, including those solar panels. I had a meeting last week, what we call a climate meeting, where we talked about what is happening in the area here, which is also part of this community we live in and how far they are about getting solar panels. Moreover, we know we must do something about the solar panels because they are quite old and ineffective" (DK-VL01).

People in this area could join different social groups to share their ideas and knowledge, learn something new, or meet new people. Therefore, social interaction among community members could motivate them to be more active in their neighbourhood and take responsibility for their community.

Also, community members at UEF were mainly students and staff at Aarhus University who followed pro-environmental behaviour in their lives, and their expectations of having a sustainable lifestyle and their awareness of the energy crisis motivated them to be part of this project. One of the students said:

"We have been told for many years that climate change is real. I think it is important with this project to show that we can do something, and maybe it is a small step, but it is a step. So I guess it is important to inform people that there is something we can do, and there is a way we can tell the government that we want to be more climate-friendly and participate in the green transition" (DK-VL05).

Additionally, this project held different meetings and discussions to raise people's awareness about the energy crisis and the role of renewable energies in producing local energy at the university. These meetings encouraged community members to be active in this project and learn how to follow pro-environmental behaviour in their lives. Related to the meetings, one of the participants noted:

"Students at the university can gather and discuss energy and climate change mitigation topics...I also wanted to reduce my CO2 footprint. Moreover, one thing is that you can ensure that the electricity you consume is more sustainable... many years ago, I was a student. I did not have enough resources to sort of buy my land where I could install solar panels or other generators. So, this is sort of one way to achieve the goal of consuming electricity that is more sustainable" (DK-VL02).

In Italy, in the case of "A Otto Minuti dal Sole" behavioural changes through participation in ESC was observed in the social benefits experienced at an individual level, particularly through the fostering of positive human relationships and a sense of community. All six participants highlighted the significant role these activities played in enhancing solidarity among individuals. Furthermore, the dissemination of values associated with sustainability was also identified. The vulnerable individuals' reason for joining this community were both social and financial, and all but one in six reported that changes resulted in energy savings, and this change was preceded by their positive attitudes towards the environment and environmental sustainability. Some of the changes were "waste management", increased recycling, and an attempt to become vegan.

It was also reported that joining an energy community helped some become more environmentally sustainable. Indeed, even though none of the vulnerable individuals have reported savings (e.g. save on electricity bill) since joining the project – since the PV system has not yet been installed – there have still been positive changes in behaviour (e.g. reduction of energy use in daily life; greater propensity to consume energy during the cheapest time slots) as a result of joining the project. At the collective level, participants are engaged in meetings and environmental events (e.g., waste management, recycling and cost analysis). The meetings helped gather and disseminate information in the neighbourhood. Furthermore, they also report pro-social benefits after joining the energy community, such as good human relationships and/or being part of a community.

In the case of "La Vele" the vulnerable participants were interested in reducing their energy cost because of the quality of care of disabled family members. They were also interested in mitigating energy poverty, environmental issues and had a sensitivity to this issue before joining the energy community. They had reduced their energy use in their homes as much as possible. Some participants in the EC have become more involved in meetings where decisions are made about the project. The participation in the EC project have been a trigger to get more involved in pro-social issues for some (e.g. solidarity and social projects). At the collective level some setbacks were reported, where

minibus service was reduced due to funding issues and participation by vulnerable individuals was passive and sporadic.

In the case of 'Critaro,' the vulnerable individuals were already interested in environmental sustainability, rising energy costs and cost-saving measures before joining the project, making these factors key motivations for their participation. The interviewees pointed out that the other beneficiaries of the EC were convinced by the mayor, who had promised significant savings in energy costs. Increased social cohesion was among the changes seen as a result of joining the "Critaro" case. Still, the cohesion resulted from simply joining the project and not from any specific action targeting social cohesion. At the collective level, participants seemed satisfied with a top-down strategy where vulnerable individuals were told what to do (filling out forms, receiving information).

The cases analysed reveal that behavioural changes at both individual and collective levels among vulnerable groups are primarily driven by economic incentives, environmental awareness and social benefits. Many individuals adopted energy-saving practices as a response to high energy costs rather than an intrinsic commitment to sustainability, as seen in Norway and Italy, where participants modified daily habits to lower their energy bills. However, in Denmark and some Italian cases, participants were already environmentally conscious before joining the projects, demonstrating that prior awareness significantly influences proactive engagement in sustainability initiatives. Across the cases, social interaction played a crucial role in fostering collective action, knowledge-sharing and a sense of community, with meetings and workshops helping to reinforce sustainable practices. Despite the positive impact of these projects, financial constraints posed significant challenges, limiting participation, delaying expected benefits, or creating maintenance burdens, particularly for renewable energy infrastructure. Additionally, engagement levels varied, with some individuals actively participating in decision-making, while others remained passive and followed top-down directives. While immediate economic benefits were not always realised, increased awareness of sustainability and community cohesion emerged as significant positive outcomes. These findings suggest that aligning economic incentives with environmental goals, fostering social inclusion and ensuring financial sustainability are significant factors in promoting long-term behavioural change within vulnerable communities.

4.2 Behavioural change at the individual and collective levels: project leaders' perspectives

In Sofienberggata 7, the project leader mentioned goals and activities in the Oslo municipality to save energy and use renewable energy sources. This can manifest in behavioural change at a collective level. He pointed out:

"The goals in the municipality are to reduce the energy consumption for municipal properties...every time we have worked with recycling waste, the community has responded very well. I think that is the best effort we make on the energy side. We are a country with a very high energy production and a very high production of clean energy. I see water-produced energy as a clean room, but so the only way we have felt the energy problem is in the prices of electrical energy...in the last four years, we have had large projects on heat pumps and installation in many buildings, which have reduced our dependence on electrical energy" (NO-PL01).

He also highlighted their goal to boost social interaction among community members by building a meeting room so that residents can join and share their concerns and opinions about the project and meet other neighbours. He said:

"Our part in the social side here is the new backyard we made with lots of meeting points and social meeting places so that more people can meet outside and enjoy the outdoors during the warm part of the year" (NO-PL01).

However, he mentioned cultural background as a hindrance to following a sustainable behavioural change on energy consumption. As he noted in the following, he is concerned that some residents who move from warmer countries to Norway tend to use more energy to keep their homes warm.

"People are fond of warmth when living here, and they talk about 24 to 28 centigrade in the living areas. Moreover, I know people from southern Europe who live here like to have the heat of 28 to 29 degrees Celsius, walking barefoot with shorts and a T-shirt in the winter. We can save much energy if you stop that behaviour" (NO-PL01).

In Bergen Ecovillage, they highlighted activities where they had to use local energy to reduce energy costs. For instance, one of the project leaders mentioned:

"Well, to live in a society where people can help each other, stimulate each other and tend to get more sustainable living and be a demonstration site so people can come and see the energy solutions, various sustainability choices. Less energy, I mean using local energy partly, at least not completely. We have few resources in general and have never quantified this to any extent. It is the environmental side of it" (NO-PL04).

Similarly, regarding producing local energy, another project leader highlighted the advantages of having local energy sources. She said:

"I guess the local energy supply will be so much cheaper than to get energy from far away, and then part of that energy is out in nature, you just need to get that energy into your house and some of the people who have visited our project and some of the people in the group have also taken some of the woods we have out there to heat their houses at home. That is such a small contribution, but the total of these minor solutions together would bring down the costs" (NO-PL02).

This project showed a strong interest in pursuing sustainable actions such as growing local food, using public transportation, carpooling and cycling. Project leaders saw these activities as encouraging pro-environmental behaviour at the individual level. For example, one of the project leaders shared the goal of building an ecovillage as a way to save more energy and grow local food. He said:

"We aim to build houses and energy solutions with cheap energy. How could we survive without energy and build houses free of poisons and plastics? I have also been growing a big part of my food since I was 18 in different places. I wanted to have a special place in the future where I could grow my food. We did a survey, and one of the seminars we had was house building, energy and growing your food, and maybe transportation also, the social aspect was one of the five top topics the people wanted to join the group" (NO-PL03).

Project leaders, in both cases, made efforts to bring community members together by organising meetings, discussion groups, various courses and workshops such as the permaculture course in Bergen Ecovillage. They aimed to increase people's understanding and awareness of sustainable

lifestyles and how they can act sustainably within a community. For example, in the Bergen Ecovillage, the project leaders organised informal monthly gatherings called *Social Friday* at the student centre in Bergen. They met with interested individuals during these gatherings to share the project plan. Additionally, they held regular open meetings, practical work gatherings (*dugnad*), and workshops on permaculture topics, wild herbs and fermentation. They also offered *tea ceremonies* once a month. These social and physical activities were their way of promoting practical permaculture solutions as a means to lead a fulfilling life with simple resources. These actions aimed to encourage pro-environmental behaviour at both the individual and collective levels.

In Denmark, project leaders at the UEF project held pro-environmental attitudes and behaviours. Most of them have stated that their motivation for being part of the project was to promote clean energy and address energy poverty. They were also driven to raise awareness about the energy crisis and advocated for sustainable energy sources and local energy production. Additionally, they were trying to engage community members through various workshops, meetings and discussions about the energy crisis, sustainable actions, and the project's goals and strategies for local energy production. One of the project leaders believed that this kind of energy community could bring students and staff to work together for a sustainable behavioural change. Affordable energy prices were another vital factor for behavioural change and motivating students to join their energy communities. She said:

"We have plans to do a lot of activities like workshops and public discussions to engage members and the community at all levels to talk about relevant topics relevant to energy and consumption... We believe this is the way to go with distributed energy generation. I thought it was an innovative way to engage people. From the start, we wanted to ensure that it was affordable for the students because students did not have a high income or could not own a house to install solar panels. So we introduced the crowdfunding model to ensure it is affordable to students. So, from the start, we said that the price for the share needs to be affordable for students" (DK-PL07).

Another project leader highlighted the high energy cost as a factor in encouraging community members to adopt pro-environmental behaviour and a behavioural change towards sustainable energy consumption. He pointed:

"People care about their wallets. So, I think the energy, the gas crisis last year, really showed that if inflation or anything like that happens, that is the only way you can make a rapid change in people's consumption and thus energy; suddenly, people started insulating their houses and finding ways to save energy because they suddenly saw a larger bill...We hope that through this project, we can show that you do not need much money to participate in the green transition" (DK-PL06).

At Solhuset, the project leaders aimed to achieve local energy production by actively involving local citizens. The board consisted of tenants committed to adopting pro-environmental behaviours such as saving energy, increasing awareness about the energy crisis, and implementing sustainable actions like recycling through workshops to engage and educate interested residents. Compared to the UEF project, citizens had less awareness of pro-environmental behaviours, particularly among vulnerable groups. Despite this, the board members expressed a desire to lead a sustainable lifestyle and encouraged other residents, especially those less interested, to participate in workshops and discussions. Regarding the meetings and workshops in Solhuset, one of the project leaders said:

"We had a general meeting with the tenants where they should or shall approve any rise in the rent. While almost 90% of the tenants said yes to the project...It was a very open dialogue, and there were several meetings. Both some information and the part where

you could say yes or no. So it is very important for us that everybody knows what they are voting for” (DK-PL01).

However, language barriers hindered the engagement of vulnerable groups, especially those who did not speak Danish. It should be noted that financial support has been given to vulnerable households who could not pay their energy bills. One of the project leaders mentioned:

“You joined the energy community, and you have the same right to have electricity for a certain amount of money. There is no prepayment. If you have problems paying your district heating bill, we normally have a procedure where you can extend the payback period. So, we have a social attitude toward low-income people if they are in need... The energy prices are high everywhere in Europe at the moment and not as expensive as two years ago... now people are more convinced that they need to check their energy bills” (DK-PL02).

In the Italian case of “A Otto Minuti dal Sole,” project leaders started the energy community with a specific interest in dealing with energy poverty. They have initiated cultural activities to strengthen the neighbourhood identity and environmental initiatives such as waste recycling and composting. Due to a lack of financial means on the part of vulnerable individuals, the project leaders consider the energy community as a tool for facilitating participation, inclusion and social cohesion. Capacity-building sessions were held to teach participants how to read energy bills correctly, reduce energy costs, and adopt behaviours that would reduce energy use. Community activities were organized to prevent families from isolating at home and using excessive energy.

The project leaders in the “Le Vele” case were motivated by the opportunity to save money and help vulnerable individuals. They reported very high energy costs and hope to save up to 60% on their energy bills. Additionally, they are trying to involve vulnerable groups from nearby areas and schools. Plans to assist vulnerable individuals are supported by financial backing from Edison Energy, and the revenues will benefit vulnerable individuals to encourage participation. Edison will also help participants reduce consumption and improve consumption behaviour, which is supported by an online platform that provides instructions. In the case of “Critaro,” the main goals are to reduce energy costs and support the transition to sustainable energy. Additionally, the project aims to improve social conditions for vulnerable individuals by bringing them together to pursue a common goal. Finally, there are plans to install a second photovoltaic (PV) system to reduce energy costs further.

From the perspective of project leaders, motivation for behavioural change in sustainability projects is driven by a combination of environmental responsibility, economic necessity and social engagement. They recognise that while their own commitment to sustainable practices is crucial, fostering behavioural change among community members requires addressing both practical and psychological barriers. Financial incentives, such as lower energy costs, often serve as strong motivators, particularly for vulnerable groups who may otherwise struggle to adopt sustainable behaviours. At the same time, leaders see the power of community-driven initiatives where collective learning and shared experiences encourage individuals to take ownership of energy consumption and sustainability efforts. By creating spaces for discussion, organising workshops, and demonstrating the benefits of local energy solutions, they aim to inspire long-term behavioural shifts. Moreover, they acknowledge the importance of cultural and social factors, understanding that sustainable change is most effective when it aligns with people’s lifestyles, needs and values. Their efforts reflect a broader vision of sustainability—not just as an environmental goal but as a tool for social cohesion, economic resilience and community empowerment.

4.3 Behavioural change at the collective level engaging policymakers

The representative from Østerøy municipality (Bergen ecovillage) was not an active member in the project. However, she believed that a clear financial plan and a clear timeline and project plan could motivate local authorities to support such projects. She noted:

"Regarding the financial part, a big player is needed. With funds to get started with the project, because it is so expensive in the start-up phase that if you do not have that funding, it struggles" (NO-P01).

Furthermore, she suggested designing a diverse physical environment, from affordable houses such as social housing to houses that meet the needs of people from various economic and social backgrounds, thereby engaging a broader range of citizens in eco-village projects.

An example of a project led and supported by the municipality is the case of Sofienberggata 7 in Oslo, financed by the Oslo municipality, which owns and operates the social housing building. They implemented sustainable strategies such as installing new ventilation systems, using solar energy on roofs and reducing energy consumption. The project team held several meetings with residents to share project timelines and results with the community and keep them informed about the project's progress. While there was no specific plan for behavioural change at a collective level, the municipality aimed to renovate the building to bring citizens together through green spaces in front of the building and by renovating the meeting halls to encourage residents to gather there and be active in society.

Regarding Danish policies, tenants' rights allow people to participate actively in community decision-making. This means that they can be involved in making decisions about energy-related matters, such as installing solar panels and insulating buildings. For example, the Solhuset project chose the board members as residents' representatives. These board members played an active role in making decisions about energy issues. They organised meetings and discussions to involve residents in decision-making and allow them to express their opinions. For the UEF project, there were no clear policies to let them install solar panels on one of the campuses of Aarhus University without considering the university as a third party. Therefore, they had some challenges at the initial stages of installing solar panels on the campus. It should be noted that there were no clear policies to define the role of vulnerable groups in energy communities in Denmark. Despite the lack of formal policies around the role of vulnerable groups in energy communities, a local authority in Denmark, a president at the National Association of Energy Communities Denmark, noted that each municipality had its own climate ambitions, aiming to bring citizens together to achieve sustainability goals. This reflects the critical role of local authorities in creating inclusive policies that enable all citizens, particularly marginalised groups, to participate in energy transitions.

The interviews with local authorities identified a strong motivation to follow pro-environmental behaviours at the collective level. Following his interview, he believed that by engaging more vulnerable individuals in energy communities, they can learn how to move toward a green transition and follow sustainable behavioural change. He said:

"I am especially working with the European definition from the European directives. People making the green transition when they are included and participate. So, depending on the big monopolies from the big companies, they can keep energy bills low" (DK-P02).

Moreover, as a member of an energy community, he worked to raise awareness about sustainable energy actions and encourage local engagement in these initiatives. His involvement highlights the importance of local leadership in driving community-wide behavioural change.

The local authorities did not play an active role in the UEF project. An interview with a representative from Aarhus municipality confirmed that the municipality did not have an active role in the project. However, the representative mentioned that the municipality has policies promoting sustainable energy actions in Aarhus. They also had several projects where citizens led and played active roles in local energy projects. regarding the energy poverty issue, as the policy stakeholder mentioned below, there is a lack of a clear definition of energy poverty and how it can be addressed within a community. He also highlighted education and awareness as well as following a democratic approach to achieve behavioural change towards sustainable energy consumption. He said:

"One of the main challenges on a national political level, I think, is the lack of focus on what energy poverty means for individual citizens. Moving from an implicit understanding of energy to a more explicit political, social, and cultural effort to organise new ways of controlling energy use is a long and difficult journey. It is not just about political challenges—there are also cultural and social ones. We need legislation with clearly formulated ambitions for a democratic approach to the green transition. It is not just about getting cars out of the city; it is also about educating citizens and creating new partnerships, including with businesses" (DK-P01).

In the Italian case of "A Otto Minuti del Sole", enablers and barriers for policymakers included the awareness of environmental issues, awareness of educational tools, and relevance of energy communities' social goals that affect authorities' support of initiatives and their lack of finances, knowledge and a lack of supportive policies. Policymakers have adopted strategies to keep people informed, educational and awareness-raising initiatives, and synergies with other projects.

In the "Le Vele" case, information is shared with vulnerable individuals through formal meetings and informal communications. Policymakers have also tried to communicate with disabled individuals, with varying levels of success. Information will also be shared with students from schools and vulnerable families in the surrounding areas once they are identified. Additionally, energy efficiency education will be implemented. The energy community of "Critaro" and the municipality have no issues with each other, and the energy community is led by a stable local authority, and there appears to be high levels of trust between the community and the municipality.

Synthesising, from the perspective of policy officers, sustainable behavioural change and participation in energy communities are shaped by both structural and social factors. Clear financial planning, well-defined policies and strong municipal engagement are seen as critical enablers, allowing local authorities to support and facilitate energy projects. Financial resources, particularly in the early stages, provide the necessary foundation for successful implementation, while inclusive decision-making structures, such as tenant participation and local governance, help foster a sense of ownership among community members. However, key barriers persist, including the lack of clear policies on energy poverty, insufficient financial support for vulnerable groups, and challenges in engaging diverse populations, particularly those with language barriers or limited awareness of energy issues. Policymakers recognize that education and awareness-raising initiatives play a crucial role in driving behavioural change, but they stress that broader legislative support and a democratic approach to energy transition are needed to create a lasting impact. While some municipalities actively promote sustainable energy actions, others remain passive, highlighting the uneven distribution of policy support across regions. Ultimately, policymakers see energy communities as a means to empower citizens, particularly marginalized groups, but acknowledge that overcoming

financial, regulatory and social challenges requires stronger coordination between national policies, local authorities and grassroots initiatives.

4.4. Subjective impact

This section synthesises information about the subjective impacts on vulnerable individuals in the cases researched, based on insights from the three categories of interviewees surveyed.

Satisfaction levels varied in the three countries investigated due to differences between energy communities and countries. In the Norwegian cases, there were some dissatisfactions, and some felt that the development of the energy community was delayed. Trust in the project leaders was high despite some issues. Some said they lacked information from project leaders. Project leaders had some problems with increased energy costs, in their opinion, due to the war in Ukraine, that they struggled with reducing. Some of the vulnerable people were critical of the political support energy communities had received and said that, globally, politicians were not interested in supporting sustainability projects like these. The agreement and satisfaction in the Norwegian cases are considered medium as there are some barriers, but the participants are dedicated and positive towards sustainability measures. Some Danish cases were also in the early stages of development, but participants had already started changing their behaviour and had adopted pro-environmental behaviours such as energy saving. Participants were involved in decision-making in the projects.

In the Italian cases, vulnerable individuals generally experienced significant subjective impacts due to their high trust in project leaders. The vulnerable groups appear to believe that participation in ECs will lead to a reduction in energy use and prices, and the high levels of inclusion of vulnerable individuals seem to explain the agreement and satisfaction. In conclusion, subjective impact was determined by trust in the project leaders, perceived assistance from policymakers, and to some degree how far advanced the energy communities were in terms of implemented measures. The individuals' attitudes had a positive effect as their pro-environmental attitudes motivated them to keep going despite setbacks in the projects.

4.5. The role of vulnerable groups in the case studies

In Norwegian cases, vulnerable groups did not have the main role in energy communities. Some of them participated in meetings and discussions to express their opinions. However, language was a barrier for those who could not speak Norwegian. We can see the same pattern for the Solhuset project, one of the Danish cases. However, some of the tenants were board members; therefore, they had an active role in their community and represented the whole community. Referring to the UEF project, another Danish case, students were identified as vulnerable groups and could become active members by participating in the crowdfunding. In the Italian cases, such as in "A Otto Minuti dal Sole," not all members were vulnerable individuals, but all were full board members with deliberative powers and were engaged in meetings, as was the case in "Critaro," where all were vulnerable individuals. In the "Le Vele" case, some vulnerable families were not yet involved, but plans had been made to involve them. In most cases, individuals' social exclusion was reduced and they had better access to information about environmental measures. Projects had not yet alleviated energy poverty or significantly reduced energy bills, as many projects were still in the early stages and had not commenced the installation of PV panels or other energy interventions.

4.6 Enablers and hindrances

Table 3 quantifies the references to factors influencing behavioural change in the interviews, revealing that knowledge, community involvement and beliefs are the most prominent factors at both individual and collective levels. Group meetings, discussions and workshops seem to enhance individuals' understanding of energy communities and promote sustainable energy consumption. In the interviews, most participants demonstrated awareness of the energy crisis and expressed interest in engaging with related projects due to their knowledge and previous experiences. Thus, both knowledge and prior experiences can be considered among the most frequently mentioned enablers of behavioural change at both individual and collective levels.

For instance, in the UEF project in Denmark, community members watched a documentary about climate change and energy-saving behaviours. Interviews with students revealed that they were eager to change their habits, as they became more concerned about their environment. They wanted to learn how to actively participate in the energy community and contribute to the project's plans and collective actions. In Norway, a notable example involves a permaculture workshop at the Bergen ecovillage, where participants embraced sustainable practices. Community members were enthusiastic about participating in the workshop and eager to learn from one another about how to grow local food. Their goal was to collaborate on local food production, which would help minimise emissions associated with transporting goods into the community.

The above examples emphasise the importance of community engagement and being part of the community to facilitate behavioural change. People can participate in various community projects; they learn from one another and collaborate on different initiatives. Participants also showed interest in actions that promote environmental sustainability (e.g. recycling, sorting waste, growing local food, and repairing old items instead of buying new ones) within a community. Developing renewable energy was one of their primary interests in joining energy communities. Interviewees exhibited specific beliefs and values, such as mutual support and collaboration towards a common goal. They also demonstrated pro-environmental attitudes and engaged in sustainable behaviours. Furthermore, their cultural values emphasise sustainability, promoting participation in energy community projects and enhancing energy efficiency. In one instance, the UEF project in Denmark, community members expressed strong trust in the project plan and its leaders because they believed that projects led by universities and researchers were inherently trustworthy. This indicates that holding a particular value can serve as a catalyst for engaging more individuals in energy communities.

On the other hand, time, policies and politics (including local, national, European and global), and financial aspects are the most mentioned hindrances to behavioural change. Some participants were dissatisfied with the projects' plans and timelines as they took more time and efforts than expected. According to the interviews, a clear project plan and timeline can foster trust among community members towards the project leaders and encourage them to take an active role in energy community projects.

Furthermore, the absence of clear policies concerning the involvement of vulnerable groups in energy communities can impede behavioural change and their participation. There is insufficient national guidance for the development of energy communities. As noted by leaders, obstacles include bureaucratic regulations and, specifically in Italy, delays in updating legislation to establish energy communities. Financial barriers also exist, such as the lack of supportive financial schemes to foster the development of energy communities, inadequate financial assistance for the engagement of vulnerable groups in these initiatives, and the absence of a clear financial blueprint to execute energy projects.

Table 3. Enablers and hindrances of behavioural change in energy communities.

	No. of interviewees in total: 57	No. of participants highlighted the factors as enablers	No. of participants highlighted the factors as hindrances	No. of participants highlighted the factors as both	Total
Individual resources (micro-level factors)	Time	2	18	0	20
	Money	8	13	2	21
	Knowledge (including awareness, experiences, know-how, information, data)	33	7	5	40
	Education (e.g., degrees, courses, providing skills/ability to deal with information, data, etc.)	20	2	0	22
	Perceived self-efficacy	25	0	1	25
	Access to equipment (e.g., tools, machines, software applications)	5	2	0	7
	Access to political and social actors	6	1	3	7
Social dynamics (meso-level factors)	Being part of a community or social network	31	3	1	34
	Having significant relationships (e.g., trust, care, support, leadership)	21	1	2	22
	Having certain beliefs and values (e.g., religious, cultural, ideological)	29	1	0	30
	Feelings of social appreciation (or lack thereof)	12	2	0	14
Structural (macro-level factors)	Physical geography and environment	10	3	7	13
	Infrastructure	9	5	2	14
	Social and economic conditions	5	10	6	15
	Policies and politics (including local, national, European, global)	11	15	5	26

	Events and developments (including local, national, European, global)	6	0	0	6
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4.8. Sustainability, replicability and scalability of the cases

4.8.1. Sustainability of impacts and changes

Sustainability here is understood as the capacity to sustain in time the actions implemented and the positive outcomes generated in the projects.

A few of the cases have not taken off; therefore, the impact of changes has been limited. Bergen Ecovillage in Norway and A Otto Minuti dal Sole in Italy have not yet installed solar panels in their communities. Also, the UEF project in Denmark is in its initial stages, so there is no possibility of measuring fully the potential impacts; nevertheless, some impacts in terms of behavioural change were already visible and were earlier described. However, other cases such as the Solhuset project in Denmark, Sofienberggata 7 in Norway, Le Vele and CRITARO are established, and they could produce local energy and develop renewable sources such as solar panels to move towards sustainable communities. Regarding the Solhuset project, trusting the project leaders and the project plan can effectively engage more residents in various community initiatives. Community members demonstrate a strong sense of belonging and actively participate in different projects because they have the right to vote on every decision affecting their community. This empowerment allows residents to take an active role and responsibility in various initiatives, such as repairing appliances at local cafes where volunteers gather to assist residents. In this case, there is also a café where residents can come together to share their concerns and thoughts about the community and get to know each other better. Activities like these bring residents together and facilitate behavioural changes at the collective level, encouraging individuals to become more involved in sustainable practices within their community and enhancing their commitment to sustainability.

Similarly, at Sofienberggata 7, various workshops are conducted, including cooking and recycling activities, where residents collaborate and connect. In line with the goals of this project, a community hall was constructed to provide a space for residents to meet, get to know each other and discuss their concerns. This initiative particularly benefits older adults and individuals with disabilities, allowing them to gather in the hall and spend quality time together. The results of the interviews indicated that there are strong community ties among members as vulnerable groups can convene in this hall, share their concerns and voice their opinions to the project leader whenever they encounter issues or have suggestions to improve living conditions in the area.

These cases demonstrate that fostering strong community ties and empowering residents to actively participate in decision-making are essential for ensuring the long-term sustainability of these initiatives. By creating shared spaces for dialogue and collaboration, such as community halls and local cafés, these projects enhance social cohesion and encourage lasting behavioural change. While some initiatives are still in their early stages, the positive engagement seen in more established projects highlights the potential for long-term impact. Strengthening trust, maintaining financial support and continuously engaging residents will be crucial in ensuring their sustainability over time.

4.8.2. Replicability and scalability of the cases

The cases of *the Solhuset and the UEF projects in Denmark, Le Vele and CRITARO in Italy, and Sofienberggata 7 in Norway*, provide successful examples of community energy schemes, offering insights into replicability and scalability. These projects highlight diverse models of energy communities, each involving different key players such as municipalities, local actors, and public institutions. The success of these projects suggests that their frameworks could be adapted and replicated in other regions, especially considering the varied contexts—from public buildings like universities (as seen in the UEF project) to neighbourhood-focused initiatives (like Sofienberggata 7). The collaboration between municipalities and local sectors, demonstrated in Norway and Italy, shows the importance of strong local governance in scaling such projects. Furthermore, the fact that the Solhuset and Le Vele are among the first energy communities in their respective countries emphasises the potential for these early models to serve as blueprints for future projects. Their scalability lies in their ability to address specific community needs while being flexible enough to be applied in different geographic and socio-economic contexts.

4.9. Outcomes on RL3 workshop – September 2024

In this workshop, we presented the results of the first and second cycles of RL3 – ACCTING as well as ACCTING fact sheets, including ‘[\[1\]](#)’ and ‘[ACCTING\[2\]](#)’. These two fact sheets are advocacy tools to bring vulnerable groups and citizens into energy communities and policy recommendations to facilitate the development of energy communities and vulnerable groups' participation.

After the presentation, there was a case study introduction in which we asked each participant to present their project goals and motivations, challenges during the implementation and development process, vulnerability profile of their community, and strategies to involve community members, especially vulnerable groups, in their projects. During this session, participants presented their cases and outcomes as well as the challenges they have faced. Then we asked members to join the panel discussion to discuss the following issues:

- What barriers and drivers do vulnerable groups face when engaging in energy communities?
- How can we enable vulnerable groups and individuals to participate in energy communities?
- What drivers and barriers affect the development of energy communities targeting energy poverty and vulnerability? How can we overcome them through targeted policies?

As participants highlighted, trust plays a crucial role in bringing together vulnerable individuals and facilitating their participation in energy communities. As one of the local authorities pointed out: “When you're vulnerable, you can be vulnerable in many ways.” Therefore, fostering trust can empower vulnerable groups to engage in energy communities. Learning from successful examples worldwide, such as energy cafés⁸ in the UK, can provide insights into building trust and involving more people in energy communities.

It was discussed that generating activities which bring people together and leaders who are trusted and inspiring for the participants is important. These events can facilitate the participation of vulnerable groups in energy communities by encouraging them to express their opinions during

⁸ More information about the energy café can be found [here](#).

meetings. Such events can showcase successful stories from various energy communities to motivate vulnerable individuals to join one.

Private companies, local authorities and energy communities could collaborate to finance and develop energy projects within a community. The power structure is a crucial element that enables or hinders the participation of vulnerable groups. For instance, it is advisable to have at least one representative from the municipalities engaging with energy communities to foster synergy with local policies in developing local energy communities. Additionally, national and regional policies should define vulnerable groups and energy communities, as the definitions may vary from country to country.

In this workshop, project leaders identified financial burdens as one of the primary obstacles to developing energy community projects. They recommended inviting sponsors capable of investing in energy communities to address the financial challenges associated with building an energy community. Additionally, other strategies, such as crowdfunding, can unite all interested community members for a project. A successful example is the UEF project, which aims to engage students by requiring only a modest investment so they can participate in the energy community and benefit from joining this initiative. Furthermore, cooperative banks can also be regarded as an alternative source of funding for energy communities, with notable examples found in Italy.

Discussion and conclusions

5. Overall discussion and conclusions

This report is based on research from three different European countries and focused on behavioural change for vulnerable individuals and project leaders at the individual and collective levels, and representatives from municipalities at the collective level in energy communities in Norway, Denmark, Italy, and Austria. In the final sample no Austrian cases were included since no suitable cases were located in the country due to a lack of inclusion of vulnerable groups. Where vulnerable groups were targeted, they had no involvement but were passive support recipients. In the other three countries, differences were found in different stages of development of the individual energy community that affected how successful it had been. For example, in Norway some projects were in very early stages and had not yet been able to reduce energy costs, but there had still been behavioural changes and attitudes towards energy-saving measures (e.g., energy use reduction). Similarly, in Denmark, energy saving was difficult to evaluate due to the early stage of one of the projects, but behavioural changes, such as an interest in seeking knowledge about pro-environmental measures were found. In Italy vulnerable groups had received education about energy-saving measures and had started to implement these in their daily lives. Vulnerable groups also displayed high levels of trust in project leaders, which positively affected their involvement. Several of the people who were involved in these energy communities had previous pro-environmental attitudes and joined due to an interest in reducing their environmental impact. This incentivised them to join energy communities and invest time and money in the projects. Financial reasons were also a driver to join energy communities, as many of the vulnerable individuals were poor, and some were disabled, as well, which increased their cost of living.

The biggest enabler of behavioural change for vulnerable individuals (see Table 3) was knowledge, which included awareness, experiences, know-how, information and data. Many vulnerable individuals may not have had access to information regarding their environmental footprint. Once informed, they might be more willing to make changes that align with sustainable practices,

particularly when this aligns with desirable financial implications such as, in this case, reducing energy bills (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002; Diekmann and Preisendörfer, 2003). Several participants in all the three countries investigated highlighted the importance of energy communities and how they had acquired knowledge about pro-environmental behaviour from their participation in meetings, discussions and workshops. This aligns with research (Dimitrova et al., 2021) that underscores how social interaction and awareness in a community (e.g. participation in meetings and discussions) can facilitate behavioural change at both individual and collective levels.

The biggest hindrance for behavioural change were time and money (see table 3). Many pro-environmental behaviours, such as investing in energy-efficient appliances or renewable energy solutions (e.g., solar panels), require upfront financial investment. Moreover, the lack of financial support for vulnerable individuals to join energy communities can act as a hindrance to behavioural change at both levels. For low-income individuals, this is a significant barrier. Vulnerable individuals have expressed their desire to receive financial support if they are to participate in a project. They are facing difficulties meeting their basic needs and cannot afford to dedicate time to a project that does not offer financial compensation or support. Other scholars (e.g. Karakislak et al., 2023; Bomberg and McEwen, 2012) have indicated that financial barriers impede community energy mobilisation and that community members who are active in projects in some instances could receive financial support.

Also, the initial costs often outweigh the potential long-term savings, making it difficult for vulnerable people to prioritise these actions when meeting immediate needs is the primary concern. Vulnerable individuals often juggle multiple responsibilities, such as balancing work, family, health issues or caregiving duties, therefore making sustainable lifestyle adjustments may not be feasible when they are already stretched thin with other obligations (Owen & Mitchell, 2011; Lorenzoni, Nicholson-Cole, & Whitmarsh, 2007). Although grants or subsidies may be available to support green actions, vulnerable individuals might lack awareness or access to these opportunities. Navigating the complex bureaucracy to access such financial incentives can be time-consuming and overwhelming.

Being part of a community or social network and for the participants to have certain beliefs and values (e.g., religious, cultural, ideological) were important enablers for behavioural change. In energy communities, individuals may feel a sense of collective responsibility and shared goals. As scholars (Rincón-Rubio & Cedano-Villavicencio, 2023) state sense of community can enable collective agency in energy communities. This collective effort could inspire personal behaviour changes as they see others in the community making similar efforts. Vulnerable individuals often rely on social networks for support. When individuals experience a sense of belonging and witness the shared commitment within the community, they are more likely to be motivated to participate in energy communities and adhere to sustainable behaviour (Rincón-Rubio & Cedano-Villavicencio, 2023). Therefore, if peers or community leaders advocate for pro-environmental actions, it may become easier for individuals to follow suit, especially when they see tangible benefits. Furthermore, being part of a community can create social norms around sustainability (Tiberio et al., 2025). If green behaviours are normalised within the group, individuals are more likely to adopt them to fit in or meet community expectations.

For some individuals, caring for the environment may be framed as a moral or community duty, and several participants had pro-environmental attitudes before joining the energy community. For example, in A Otto Minuti dal Sole, where five of the six individuals had previous pro-environmental attitudes, and all participants reported behavioural changes after joining ECs. Therefore, it seems that individuals' pre-existing values around environmentalism influenced their behaviour when given the opportunity or resources to act.

Certain beliefs and values regarding the environment can facilitate the adoption of pro-environmental behaviours. Immigrants, for example, may draw from traditions in their countries of origin that

emphasise sustainability, such as frugal living or resource conservation. These values can facilitate the easier adoption of pro-environmental behaviours in their new communities. Some participants considered self-efficacy an enabler, and this could be linked to their ability to organise and do specific tasks within their community (Mashinchi and Ravesloot, 2022). According to Depp (1993), being motivated to participate in a community project can enhance people's ability to contribute to community development activities. Furthermore, their beliefs and attitudes about their capabilities and how they can engage in their community can influence their self-assessment of how they can actively participate and have a voice in their community (Depp, 1993).

Political decisions at different levels (local, national, European, global) may not be aligned, creating confusion and barriers for vulnerable individuals who wish to adopt pro-environmental behaviours. For example, conflicting regulations on energy tariffs, waste management or green technology adoption can leave individuals uncertain about the best course of action. Political inaction, delays in implementing green infrastructure, or insufficient funding for energy programmes can all contribute to limiting the opportunities for individuals to engage in sustainable behaviours.

Overall, the findings highlight how knowledge, social engagement and financial incentives significantly influence behavioural change in energy communities, particularly among vulnerable individuals. Access to clear information and education about sustainable practices was shown to enable positive shifts in behaviour, especially when supported by trusted community leadership and strong social networks. However, considerable barriers remain, such as limited financial resources, insufficient policy alignment across different governance levels, and practical challenges in balancing immediate needs against long-term sustainability goals.

Based on results from the energy communities in the three countries researched, changes should be implemented in several areas, such as the energy communities themselves, including more vulnerable individuals with project leaders in decision-making, if possible, as well as in sustainable community activities. Policymakers should be also more directly involved in order to understand better the needs and challenges of vulnerable individuals' participation in community energy projects. The results of this research indicate that involving vulnerable individuals in decision-making processes encourages greater participation in pro-environmental actions and helps them improve their circumstances. This leads to their investment of time and effort in energy communities, rather than remaining passive recipients of external support. Inclusion appeared to positively affect participants' knowledge of how to make their behaviours more sustainable, such as reducing energy consumption and improving waste management.

A currently unanswered question is how to include vulnerable individuals who do not possess pro-environmental attitudes, are unaware or uninterested in environmental issues, or lack the financial means or time due to work or childcare commitments. Additionally, some vulnerable individuals with mental or physical health conditions may face obstacles to inclusion and can be difficult to reach. These challenges could potentially be addressed on multiple levels by other vulnerable individuals reaching out within their communities, to friends and family, thereby informing them about the benefits of ECs. Project leaders may have access to broader networks that are out of reach for individuals and are advised to collaborate with policymakers who can implement policy changes based on the experiences of both vulnerable individuals and project leaders in ECs.

The importance of using information from and building on the successes of already established projects should be considered important. The challenges faced by project leaders of successful initiatives during the initial phase, such as funding and bureaucracy, along with the solutions they adopted, should inform potential energy communities currently in the planning phase of a new project. For those who are not sensitive to environmental issues, the focus can be placed on the financial

benefits, which in some projects might be substantial. Some participants had strictly financial motives, and cost reduction is important for individuals who struggle with low-income and high living costs.

5.1. Gender+ intersectional (in)equalities

In the second research cycle, we aimed to improve the representation of women in our study across Norway, Italy and Denmark. This focus was informed by existing research indicating women are often underrepresented in energy communities, both in participation and decision-making (Dudka, 2024; Tsagkari, 2022). By engaging more women, we sought to understand the barriers they face, their motivations for involvement and potential strategies to promote greater gender inclusivity in community energy projects. This approach allowed us to compare gendered experiences in energy communities and their intersection with energy poverty.

Findings from specific cases revealed varying degrees of female participation. In some energy communities, such as Bergen Ecovillage (Norway), Solhuset and the UEF projects (Denmark), and Le Vele (Italy), women were actively involved in decision-making processes. This suggests that certain organisational structures or cultural contexts may facilitate greater female agency. However, female participation was less prominent in other cases, such as Sofienberggata 7 (Norway), Otto Minuti dal Sole and CRITARO (Italy). This prompted efforts to involve more women in our research to ensure a more representative understanding of gendered experiences within these initiatives.

While our study successfully captured a range of female perspectives, it is important to acknowledge the absence of self-identified LGBTQI+ participants. This gap highlights a potential limitation in our sampling approach or the unwillingness of LGBTQI+ individuals to disclose their identities within the context of energy communities. Future research could explore how intersectional identities—including gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status and ethnicity—shape access to and participation in energy communities, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of structural inequalities in these spaces.

5.2 “Better stories” and links to transformation

Based on interviews conducted across Norway, Denmark and Italy, the following stories highlight how energy communities are transforming lives, especially for vulnerable populations, and driving a more inclusive energy transition. These stories can be considered better than others in these three countries.

- Bergen Ecovillage in Norway

Bergen Ecovillage is a successful example of a case study that involved most community members in different community projects. Even though it could not take off because of financial obstacles, community members are people from different socio-economic backgrounds interested in building a sustainable society where people trust each other, collaborate in community projects and help each other for the green transition. Regarding the societal transformation, there were different meetings, discussions and workshops with community members to collaborate and learn about sustainable living and local energy production. For instance, a permaculture workshop has been carried out in this ecovillage to grow local food and enhance social ties among members. The interested individuals had prior knowledge about energy saving, renewable energies and sustainable lifestyles. These acted as main enablers to join this project and participate in community events and meetings.

- The UEF project in Denmark

This project is a good example of engaging students in energy communities. There is significant collaboration and engagement in decision-making. Several meetings, discussions and workshops have been conducted to engage community members in the energy project. Regarding the financial plan for the project development, crowdfunding has been followed to bring students, university staff and citizens together to be part of the project. As one of the students stated, “Crowdfunding is a great thing because you can invest a very small amount of money even though you participate in something great. So, it is also a way of communicating to everybody that you can do something”(RL3-DK-VL03). Community members believed that the project leaders were committed to maintaining transparency through every stage and decision, ensuring that community members were well-informed and could actively participate in meetings, discussions and workshops.

- Solhuset (part of a bigger project of the Energifællesskab Avedøre) in Denmark

This project is the first citizen energy community in Denmark. Community members are mainly from low-income groups in this social housing. The board members in the Solhuset project consist of candidates who represent all tenants in this society. They have regular meetings and discussions at the board meeting, and as they pointed out, they actively participate in any decision-making within the community. The language in the meetings was aligned with the tenants' understanding, and therefore, people were interested in joining the projects' meetings. People also showed trust in project leaders and the board members because they represent the whole community. Regarding the supportive policy, we can refer to the Tenant democracy, which allows community members to participate actively in the decision-making process within their community. This policy can encourage citizens to have a voice in community energy projects, and therefore, it can cause behavioural change at both levels.

- CRITARO in Italy

CRITARO is the first renewable and solidarity energy community in Calabria. The project is well established, led by a stable local authority, and supported by one of the most experienced companies in the sector. There appears to be high trust between the ESC associates and the municipality. A clear project plan and timeline promoted trust between community members, project leaders and the municipality. Financial support was also provided to develop this project. Regarding the vulnerable group's participation in this project, all the families involved in this project (disadvantaged families living in social housing) are active members, and they participate regularly in meetings and discussions to express their opinions and be informed about the project's progress. Regarding the concept of the theory of change in this case study, we can refer to the community engagement and active participation of vulnerable groups in the energy community as well as behavioural change at both individual and collective levels, such as reduced energy consumption and higher use of energy-efficient appliances, energy saving in their homes to reduce energy costs, and social cohesion among community members.

5.3 Policy crossovers

The ACCTING project researchers carried out eight different “research lines (RLs)” and this report cover number three. There are possible overlaps between the eight RLs that cover vulnerable individuals and how the GD has influenced them.

Research line 4 investigated barriers and enablers to implement environmental measures for micro-entrepreneurs. Similar to energy communities they struggled with funding from authorities and would

be helped by more directed funds for their businesses as energy communities would be similarly helped by more attention from local and national policymakers. This reflects some issues in energy communities where money was seen as a barrier. In cases where low-income individuals are included or where energy communities struggle with funding from municipalities or national governments, it can be important.

Moreover, Research Line 5 focuses on improving food security and promoting healthy diets in vulnerable communities through local production, informed consumption practices, and circularity. This line of research emphasises food security and provides examples such as community gardens in Turkey and Portugal. One of the case studies from Research Line 3, the Bergen Ecovillage, conducted a workshop called a permaculture course to educate community members on growing local food. Participants cultivated various vegetables locally, with the main goal of connecting with nature and providing local food to minimise energy consumption associated with transportation.

5.4 Research gaps and directions for future research

5.4.1. Challenges and opportunities

Some challenges/opportunities might be envisaged in terms of comparability of cases, for example:

- Different stages of development of the projects. In this case, it was important to find common grounds for comparability beyond the current stage of development. For example, a mature project might still present useful information regarding barriers and drivers that affected its early stage of development to the point of influencing its mature stage. Gathering information about the set-up stage offered the chance to compare a mature project with projects still at the set-up stage.
- Different scale of the projects: some energy communities have been developed to a large scale in terms of membership base. This raised some questions in terms of comparability. Nevertheless, being mindful of the different scales of membership might allow for tailored questions capable of highlighting specific barriers and drivers related to the size of the membership base, therefore providing valuable insights on the relevance of this variable for community energy projects.
- Local/national policies context. Inevitably, contexts were different, but this could enhance the comparisons' outputs, showing how some barriers or drivers present in a context but missing in another one determined different outcomes.
- Urban/rural contexts. Diversity of context, i.e., urban, rural or semirural contexts, presented different characteristics capable of influencing the community energy schemes differently. Again, being mindful of this was an opportunity to highlight the diverse barriers and drivers acting forces in different contexts.
- Social housing vs. non-social housing. It had been agreed that including social housing energy communities in our selection of cases was desirable to increase the understanding of how low-income individuals hosted in social housing projects were included in community energy projects.
- Lead or not by local authorities. Certain community energy schemes involving low-income individuals were led or initiated by local authorities. This difference impacted the barriers and

drivers at the project's initial and possibly follow-up stages. Such a variable needed to be considered in our data collection to ascertain what role local authorities played and if the obvious advantages due to their involvement are matched by some limitations for the community projects.

5.4.2. Limitations of the study

- Semi-structured interviews with a limited number of participants in selected energy communities may restrict the generalisability of findings. However, we were unable to find more individuals for the interviews due to the following reasons:
 - Some energy communities were at the early stages, so there were no more participants to conduct the interviews.
 - Language barriers may prevent interviewing vulnerable individuals who are not fluent in English. Some interviewees were immigrants who could not speak English, Norwegian or Danish.
- Semi-structured interviews capture the perceptions and experiences at a specific point in time, making it difficult to gather longitudinal data to assess changes in behaviour at both collective and individual levels for participants who were part of communities in the early stages of development.
- Quantitative validation of the research (e.g. survey) was limited due to the small number of participants in the energy communities.
- Cross-national comparisons can be difficult due to varying national policies and regulations. The success of energy communities depends on these national policies, which is why we might see successful cases in Italy and unsuccessful cases in Norway. However, knowing the different national policies can also be of valuable insight.
- There may be a gap in measuring the impacts, such as energy poverty mitigation, in selected energy communities, as this can be seen as a long-term effect.

5.4.3. Research gaps

We have identified some research gaps that our current research was not able to reveal but would be interesting to further investigate.

- The different energy communities were at different stages during our visits; therefore, it would be interesting to follow these cases over a larger timeframe to be able to identify other enablers or barriers that can only be seen through changes over time.
- A longitudinal study would allow for an evaluation of long-term effects and be able to see the effects on energy poverty.

5.5 Directions for policy recommendations

- Improved political local support (e.g., municipalities) for establishing community energy projects should be given to facilitate collaboration between private companies, the local sector, and local communities to develop projects.
- Vulnerable groups often feel too weak to participate in meetings and discussions and express their opinions; supportive strategies should encourage them to participate in decision-making.

- Participant compensation for vulnerable individuals to participate in meetings and express their opinions and needs, empowering them to have an active voice in their communities. Facilities should be provided for meetings in English for immigrants (or even their mother tongue) who cannot speak Italian, Norwegian, or Danish in energy communities.
- Ensure that energy communities adhere to a democratic decision-making process in their project leadership.
- Offer free or subsidised training programmes for community members to learn how to maintain renewable energy systems (e.g., solar panels on roofs).
- Project financing has been a barrier for some projects, and the costs of establishing environmental measures have been limiting. Direct financial support towards vulnerable individuals joining energy communities should be provided to assist in financing sustainable energy interventions.
- Clear policies and guidelines related to vulnerable groups' collaboration in energy communities can facilitate their participation in such projects.
- Implement behavioural change programmes with rewards, such as offering discounts on energy bills to households that adopt sustainable energy consumption practices or install energy-efficient appliances. Conduct environmental impact assessments before and after establishing energy communities to minimise negative effects on the physical and social environment.
- Conduct community needs assessments before the project implementation can empower community members to have voices in decision-making process.

References

- Bergen Økologiske Landsby. (2019). *Et rikt liv med enkle midler: Bergen Økologiske Landsby*.
- Bergen Økologiske Landsby. (2022). *Prosjektbeskrivelse, kortversjon, med vekt på gjennomføring og finansiering; Bergen Økologiske Landsby og Ledaal Eiendom*.
- Bomberg, E., & McEwen, N. (2012). Mobilizing community energy. *Energy Policy*, 51, 435-444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.08.056>
- Chabay, I. (2020). Vision, identity, and collective behavior change on pathways to sustainable futures. *Evolutionary and Institutional Economics Review*, 17(1), 151-165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40844-020-00183-2>
- Cunha, F. B. F., Carani, C., Nucci, C. A., Castro, C., Silva, M. S., & Torres, E. A. (2021). Transitioning to a low carbon society through energy communities: Lessons learned from Brazil and Italy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 75, 101994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.101994>
- Depp, M. J. (1993). *Leadership self-efficacy and community involvement* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). The Pennsylvania State University.
- Diekmann, A., & Preisendörfer, P. (2003). Green and greenback: The behavioral effects of environmental attitudes in low-cost and high-cost situations. *Rationality and Society*, 15(4), 441-472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043463103154003>
- Dimitrova, A., Vaishar, A., & Štaštná, M. (2021). Preparedness of young people for a sustainable lifestyle: Awareness and willingness. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137204>
- Dudka, A. (2024). Women in energy communities: An intersectional analysis of their participation. In *Women and the energy sector: Gender inequality and sustainability in production and consumption* (pp. 243-262). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-26862-5_14
- EBO Consult. (2020, December 15). Denmark's first energy cooperative. <https://eboconsult.dk/en/2020/12/15/denmarks-first-energy-cooperative-is-officially-approved/>
- EBO Consult. (2024). EBO Consult and energy communities. <https://eboconsult.dk/en/energifaelleskab/>
- Futurebuilt. (2023). Sofienberggata 7. <https://www.futurebuilt.no/Forbildeprosjekter#!/Forbildeprosjekter/Sofienberggata-7>
- Hagger, M. S., Cameron, L. D., Hamilton, K., Hankonen, N., & Lintunen, T. (Eds.). (2020). *The handbook of behavior change*. Cambridge University Press.
- He, R., Jin, J., Qiu, X., Zhang, C., & Yan, J. (2023). Rural residents' climate change perceptions, personal experiences, and purchase intention–behavior gap in energy-saving refrigeration appliances in Southwest China. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 98, 106967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2023.106967>

Heiskanen, E., Johnson, M., Robinson, S., Vadovics, E., & Saastamoinen, M. (2010). Low-carbon communities as a context for individual behavioural change. *Energy Policy*, 38(12), 7586-7595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.07.023>

Karakislak, I., Sadat-Razavi, P., & Schweizer-Ries, P. (2023). A cooperative of their own: Gender implications on renewable energy cooperatives in Germany. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 96, 102947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.102947>

Kauppi, S. (2015). *Behavior change and communication: A descriptive literature review of behavior change and communication in Sub-Saharan countries*.

Kollmuss, A., & Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the gap: Why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental Education Research*, 8(3), 239-260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620220145401>

Kuznik, M. (2024). *Exploring the success factors of renewable energy communities: A social-psychological perspective*(Master's thesis, University of Twente).

Köhlin, G., Sills, E. O., Pattanayak, S. K., & Wilfong, C. (2011). Energy, gender and development: What are the linkages? *Where is the evidence?*

Ledaal Eiendom AS, & Bergen Økologiske Landsby SA. (2022). *Videre fremdrift for utbyggingsprosjektet Bruvik Aust 2022*.

Linnér, B. O., & Wibeck, V. (2019). *Sustainability transformations across societies: Agents and drivers across societies*. Cambridge University Press.

Lorenzoni, I., Nicholson-Cole, S., & Whitmarsh, L. (2007). Barriers perceived to engaging with climate change among the UK public and their policy implications. *Global Environmental Change*, 17(3-4), 445-459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2007.01.004>

Marchi, L., Felicioni, L., Sabatini, F., & Errante, L. (2023). Exploring energy literacy in Italian social housing: A survey of inhabitants preparing the ground for climate transition. *Sustainability*, 15(11), 8544. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15118544>

Mashinchi, G., & Ravesloot, C. (2022). Memory self-efficacy and community participation. *Graduate Student Journal of Psychology*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.3233/GSJ-2022-1041>

Owen, A. L., & Mitchell, G. (2011). Outside influence – Some effects of retrofit insulation on social networks, social norms and household energy practices. *Energy Policy*, 39(1), 645-654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.10.007>

Pellegrini-Masini, G. (2020). *Wind power and public engagement: Co-operatives and community ownership*. Routledge.

Purvis, B., Mao, Y., & Robinson, D. (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: In search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science*, 14, 681-695. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-0672-0>

Rincón-Rubio, A. G., & Cedano-Villavicencio, K. G. (2023). Emotional energy communities: Centering emotions and feelings within energy transitions in southern Mexico. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 98, 103014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103014>

Steg, L., Perlaviciute, G., & Van der Werff, E. (2015). Understanding the human dimensions of a sustainable energy transition. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 805. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00805>

Tiberio, L., Kirchler, B., Massullo, C., Carrus, G., Haider, J., Kollmann, A., & Caffaro, F. (2025). Unveiling the power of social norms interventions: Investigating energy savings behavior in an Italian energy cooperative. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 122, 103989. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.103989>

Tsagkari, M. (2022). The need for a gender-based approach in the assessment of local energy projects. *Energy for Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2022.02.004>

Tvaronaciene, M., & Slusarczyk, B. (Eds.). (2019). *Energy transformation towards sustainability*. Elsevier.

Appendix

Appendix A: Second research cycle RL3

Criteria for selection of cases

Criteria for selecting energy communities.

Energy communities do not present an agreed definition. Some authors adopt regulatory definitions, while others propose general definitions, for example, the following:

“...social and organizational structures formed to achieve specific goals of its members primarily in the cleaner energy production, consumption, supply, and distribution, although this may also extend to water, waste, transportation, and other local resources.”¹

In this project, we adopt a broad view of energy communities in agreement with the above definition, and thereby, we mean *any local participatory process led or actively participated by citizens that aims at increasing the sustainable use or production of energy.*

We envisage selecting 2-3 cases per country, i.e. ten overall cases across Norway, Austria, Denmark and Italy.

The energy communities would be either:

- a. Successfully established
 - i. deliberately addressing the aim of reducing energy poverty or
 - ii. not designed to address energy poverty but that delivered results to reduce energy poverty.
- b. In the making: a community energy project that is at the early developmental stage
- c. Unsuccessful
 - i. projects that didn't take off, or
 - ii. projects that haven't achieved energy poverty results yet
- d. **IF** cases were impossible to identify, then an alternative could be to conduct research in an area where it would be present a community of energy vulnerable individuals that would be potentially interested in joining an energy community aimed at reducing energy poverty

Further criteria for selection:

1. *Addressing energy poverty or energy vulnerability.* The community energy project should implement actions to decrease energy poverty and/or energy vulnerability.
2. *Vulnerability.* Individuals deemed vulnerable following the classification earlier employed in the ACCTING project (see D2.1). In RL3, among others, we envisage relevant vulnerabilities regarding economic disadvantage, ethnic background, old or young age, living in a rural or remote location (islands), and gender.
3. *Collective active participation of vulnerable citizens (in various degrees, i.e. low to high).* As highlighted in the adopted definition, the active involvement of citizens is a paramount feature

for selection. The project might have been initiated by municipalities, ONG or any other third-sector organisation concerned with alleviating energy poverty. Still, vulnerable citizens must actively participate and not be mere recipients of actions carried out by other subjects.

Appendix B: Country level report (Austria)

Authors: Martin Felix Gajdusek, Olga Bolibok, ZSI - Centre for Social Innovation

Despite the project team's efforts, no community was found in Austria that can be activated and met the research criteria for active participation of vulnerable groups. The efforts were not successful, and we could not identify energy communities that target energy poverty and engage vulnerable populations such as low-income households, minority groups, and elderly individuals. The Austrian team has approached also other initiatives but with no response. While many communities had plans to address energy poverty, none had successfully implemented these initiatives or ensured the active involvement of vulnerable groups in decision-making or governance.

Reasons for the non-success of activating appropriate cases include following structural reasons influencing the work of those setting up energy communities: (1) Pressure within the energy communities with slowly moving to regular operations leading to limited room for experimentation and in view of the newness of legal and technical processes. Only most recently templates and other tools have become available to enable regular operations; (2) Initiatives' access to vulnerable persons and their non-interest in view of other overarching pressing issues in the life course. Access to information about households confronted with energy poverty is strictly confidential; (3) According to the local Authority of Lower Austria that was visited by a team member the rather new developments but also requirements for set up and own risk taking of EEG's limit participation beyond technical enthusiast, often in a combination with missing legal experience. Moreover, is the lack of best practice examples as role model a factor, a missing source of inspiration. Also, the e-5 municipalities follow energy related targets and do not include social circumstances. Information concerns also the current influence of developers (consultant companies) that facilitate the build-up of PV energy communities using standard contracts, standard calculation tools based on the APIs of energy providers that do not integrate (individual) social tariffs. (4) A recent development is the setup of PV installations by the electricity providers and lease of the roof against reduced electricity prices. As an effect, the house owners can not join as prosumers an energy community. (5) finally, the above described "price rally" does affect all existing and future energy communities. The unexpected rise of a five-fold rise of electricity prices in 2022/23 creates a volatile and demotivating situation especially for the new energy communities that must communicate clearly prices in advance or fix (high) price rates on a usually quarterly basis in retrospective way leaving the prosumers and consumers in a situation of unknown prices.

The currently funded Solidarity Energy Communities, such as Energy WITH Spirit, Energy Donations, and SOL:E, aim to support socially disadvantaged and vulnerable groups, including low-income households and refugees. While they focus on addressing energy poverty by providing benefits like reduced energy costs and donations, these communities do not meet the criteria for active participation (but experimenting with a top-down approach and currently run as funded projects). The SOL:E project research barriers preventing vulnerable groups from participating in energy communities. Their findings relate to the conclusions of our initial research, showing the existing barriers¹⁹. Vulnerable groups, although beneficiaries, are primarily passive recipients rather than actively involved in decision-making or governance. This situation is largely attributed to their community's context and the structure of the projects.

The motivation to form energy communities in Austria is generally cost savings, environmental benefits, energy supply security but not specifically targeting energy-poor or vulnerable populations.

Appendix C: Gender+ intersectional approach in RL3

We aim to involve more women in our recruitment process for interviews in Norway, Denmark, Italy, and Austria. It is important to allow them to express their viewpoints and discuss their challenges, motivations for participating in the projects, and suggestions for increasing involvement in community energy projects. By doing so, we can gain different perspectives on our related topics, leading to a comparative study of gender approaches to community energy projects and the issue of energy poverty. Gender differences are evident in women's understanding of energy issues and their level of participation in meetings and discussions. Their perspective on their community can help identify the enablers and hindrances to their involvement in community energy projects. A society's social, cultural, economic, and political context can influence women's participation in community energy projects. The following questions can address the gender perspective in research line three of the ACCTING project.

- Demographic questions
 - Have the organisers created opportunities for you and others in the community to share your opinions and/or give feedback about the project?
 - Of all the information that you received, what specific information helped you make the decision to join the project?
 - Have you encountered any challenges or barriers in accessing information related to this project? If so, can you describe them?
 - Do you receive any benefits from having joined (being part of) the project? If yes, what kind of benefit?
 - Did you have any constraints that made it difficult for you to actively participate in the project?
 - What barriers or challenges do you think prevent some community members from fully participating in and benefiting from energy projects?
 - Do you get involved in any other activities in your neighbourhood? What activities?

Suppose they are the primary breadwinners for their families. In that case, we can analyse the following questions based on their ability to manage their own lives and provide strategies for empowering women in community energy projects.

- Can you tell me how you keep your home warm during cold days (and/or cool during hot days)?
- Before joining the project, were energy costs affordable for you and/or your family?

Consent form

Participant information and consent form

ACCTING – AdvanCing behavioural Change Through an INclusive Green deal (GA n. 101036504)

1. Introduction

My name is [Interviewer's name] and I am a researcher at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway. I am contacting you to invite you to participate in an interview for a study within ACCTING, a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 framework programme.

I am contacting you to ask if you would like to participate in an interview about the energy environment and energy poverty in Norway.

2. Purpose of research

The aim of ACCTING is to learn from and promote innovations that promote sustainable social and behavioral change. The research focuses on the European Green Deal's policies and interventions, which we hope to make more equitable and inclusive.

You and your experiences are important to our qualitative research. The AACTING researchers conduct these interviews to collect interviews in 4 countries at the same time (Norway, Italy, Denmark and Austria).

3. Project participant and right to withdraw

If you agree to participate, it means participating in one interview that will last approximately one hour. The interview can be conducted online or offline, in a public place of your choice, and will be conducted in English. The interview will be audio recorded, transcribed and pseudonymised. This means that we will exchange identifying information in the data with a pseudonym. This keeps your identity confidential, but allows us to re-identify you later if necessary. The audio recording will be destroyed no later than two years after the end of the project. NTNU's research team members are the only ones who will have access to the audio recording and transcription. The only data shared with the larger ACCTING consortium is a pseudonymised report in English.

Your participation in the interview is completely voluntary. It is your choice whether you want to participate or not. Before you start answering the questions, the information in this document must be given to you. You will be asked to either read or listen carefully to me as I read it, and sign it to consent, either in print, electronically or via voice recording.

You can withdraw your consent and opt out of the interview at any time, and you can do so without any explanation and without consequences for your relationship with NTNU or ACTUELLE partners. You don't have to answer questions you don't want to. You have the right to withdraw the data you have provided (or remove parts of it), including your personal data: however, it is not possible to remove data that has already been used with your permission in publications, reports or open datasets. If you wish to exercise your right to withdraw after this interview, you must contact the principal investigator, without having to explain why you wish to withdraw (contact details below).

4. Procedure

We expect you to answer the questions in a free, clear and honest way, and describe your personal experiences with the energy society and energy poverty in Norway. At the end of the interview, some demographic questions will be asked to obtain information about your age, education and employment status, nationality, length of residence in the area, language, religion, gender and relationship status. NTNU ACCTING members will analyze this data to understand the distribution and spread of interviewees in the selected communities. You can keep these questions without any explanation if you feel uncomfortable. No one other than the interviewer/listener will be present unless you yourself want someone else to be there. When the interview is finished, the recording will be transcribed and pseudonymised as described above.

5. Data protection

All project ACCTING activities comply with General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and the Norwegian Law on the Processing of Personal Data (Personal Data Act) of 15 June 2018. All personal data collected will be kept secure, and no personal data will be kept for longer than necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. Personal data which is no longer required for the purposes of the ACCTING project will be deleted, and all recordings will be deleted two years after the end of the project, at the very latest.

Most importantly, we use your personal data only with your permission. To exercise your rights to access, rectify, erase, and restrict your personal data, you can contact:

Thomas Helgesen – NTNU Data protection officer

Email: thomas.helgesen@ntnu.no

Phone: +47 93079038

6. Anonymity and confidentiality

We will only use your personal data for the purpose specified above, and we will process your personal data in accordance with data protection legislation (the GDPR). The personally identifiable information gathered via the interview will be kept in the strictest confidentiality and will be safely stored and destroyed two years after the end of the project, at the latest. The planned end date of the project is September 2025. Only the NTNU research team will have access to non-pseudonymised data. We will replace your name and contact details with a code. The list of names, contact details and respective codes will be stored separately from the rest of the collected data. Your personal data will be kept confidential and will only be disclosed to the wider team of the ACCTING project on a need-to-know basis, after requesting your explicit consent. It will not be disclosed to any other individual or third parties.

7. Possible risks, disadvantages or discomfort, incidental findings

Your participation in this research does not present any physical or psychological risks or risks of disadvantages and does not intend any discomfort.

You should be aware that any criminal activity witnessed or uncovered during research must be reported to the responsible and appropriate authorities, even if this means overriding commitments to maintain your confidentiality and anonymity.

8. Benefits of this research project

While there are no immediate benefits from your participation, the ACCTING project will use the knowledge from the interviews to produce solutions for policy, practice, and future research agendas, and disseminate scientific and policy-relevant knowledge on biodiversity, clean energy, climate action, sustainable food, and sustainable mobility, with the aim of reducing inequalities.

9. Project Results

The results of the study will be disseminated for scientific purposes in compliance with the ethical standards of the scientific community. It is guaranteed that the reports and scientific outcomes related to this project will not contain any identifying markers.

You will be able to see the results of the study. These will be reported to the European Commission, in research articles and on repository platform for EC funded research. Raw data (audio recordings and transcripts) will not be made publicly available, only the analysis of data when it is possible to protect the privacy and anonymity of individuals. Some research results and news items will be posted on the project website: <https://accting.eu>

10. Questions and claims

If you have any questions about the research or if you would like to make a complaint about how you have been treated during your participation in this project, please contact the Principal Investigator (contact below),

who will process it quickly and carefully. If you are unsatisfied with the way your complaint is being handled, you can also contact Dr Ildiko Ipolyi, the ACCTING Coordinator (iipolyi@esf.org).

11. Organisation and Research Funding

ACCTING has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036504.

12. What gives us the right to process your personal data?

We will process your personal data based on your consent. Based on an agreement with NTNU, The Data Protection Services of Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research has assessed that the processing of personal data in this project meets requirements in data protection legislation. If you have questions about how data protection has been assessed in this project by Sikt, contact: · email: (personverntjenester@sikt.no) or by telephone: +47 73 98 40 40.

13. Contact for more information:

ACCTING Scientific Manager	ACCTING Principal Investigator
Sofia Strid, Sofia.strid@oru.se +46(0)19303442	Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini, giuseppe.p.masini@ntnu.no +47 98079798

PARTICIPANT STATEMENT

First, I confirm that I have been invited to participate in the ACCTING project and that I consent voluntarily to be interviewed for the purposes of this study.

Second, I confirm that I have read (or been read to) the foregoing information, and I have been properly informed by [Interviewer’s name], a researcher in this project. I have received and understood the information provided about the content, purposes, and benefits of this project. I had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction. Therefore, I am aware that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. I understand that the recording and any transcript of the interview will be kept by NTNU research team only and destroyed two years after the end of the project, at the latest. I understand and agree that other authorised researchers may use my data in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs, on the condition that they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.

Name of Participant (Interviewer?)

